

Master Thesis

Carbon cycle analysis of an extensively managed floodplain along the Morava River

submitted by

Dietmar BAUER, B. Sc.
11823957

in the framework of the Master programme

067 431 Water Management regarding Climate Change

in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the academic degree

Master of Science

Vienna, May 2026

Supervisor

Assoc.Prof.Priv.Doz.DI Dr.nat.techn. Hans Peter Rauch
Institute of Soil Bioengineering and Landscape Construction
Department of Landscape, Water and Infrastructure
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna

Co-supervisors

Dipl.-Ing. Dipl.-Ing. Dr.techn. Bakk.techn. Magdalena
Von Der Thannen
Institute of Soil Bioengineering and Landscape
Construction
Department of Landscape, Water and Infrastructure
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences,
Vienna

MSc. Anna Lindenberger
Institute of Soil Bioengineering and Landscape
Construction
Department of Landscape, Water and Infrastructure
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna

Affidavit

I declare under oath that I have written this master's thesis independently and have not used any sources or aids other than those indicated. All ideas that have been taken verbatim or in their fundamental content from unpublished texts or published literature, or generated with artificial intelligence, are properly marked, cited, and provided with precise source references. The present work has not been submitted, either in whole or in part, in the same or similar form to any educational institution as a requirement for the award of an academic degree. It fully complies with the guidelines of Academic Integrity and the principles of Good Scientific Practice.

Vienna, 22.05.2026

Dietmar BAUER, BSc

Acknowledgements

In the foreword to this thesis, I would like to highlight the support, guidance, and encouragement of many people, to whom I want to express my gratitude.

First, I would like to thank my supervisor, Assoc. Prof. Priv. Doz. DI Dr. nat. techn. Hans Peter for his guidance, scientific advice, and valuable feedback throughout the development of this thesis.

I would also like to thank my co-supervisor, Dipl.-Ing. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. techn. Bakk. techn. Magdalena Von Der Thannen, for her introduction to measurement techniques, guidance with fieldwork, methodological advice and constructive feedback during the writing process of this thesis.

A very special thank you goes to MSc. Anna Lindenberger for her introduction to the collection, analysis and interpretation of greenhouse gas measurements, for her organisational support of the measurement work, and for her advice and helpful criticism during the development of the methodology and the writing process of this study.

I would also like to thank my colleagues and fellow student employees at the Institute of Soil Bioengineering and Landscape Construction for the supportive working environment and stepping in at short notice for measurement work. I would particularly like to thank Silvia Heufler, BSc, who's parallel master's thesis formed a sister study to this work. She supported me throughout the measurement work, methodological considerations and the completion of this thesis. The constant exchange of ideas and discussion with her has greatly enhanced the value of this work.

Finally, my deepest gratitude goes to my family and friends for their encouragement and reliable support throughout my studies.

Abstract

Riparian ecosystems such as floodplain grasslands store a large part of global soil carbon stocks relative to their surface area. Yet the role of riparian ecosystems as nature-based climate solutions to promote climate change mitigation remains poorly studied. Their net climate effect is uncertain due to strong spatio-temporal variability in greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes among differing climatic conditions. GHG fluxes are subject to complex hydrological and biogeochemical processes, strongly affected by soil temperature, soil moisture and groundwater dynamics. In particular, fluctuating hydrological conditions, which are characteristic of riparian ecosystems, have a strong influence on greenhouse gas (GHG) dynamics by alternately enhancing aerobic respiration or creating anaerobic conditions associated with methane (CH₄) production. To close existing knowledge gaps on GHG dynamics in riparian ecosystems and to support the development of sustainable land management practices, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and CH₄ fluxes, related environmental parameters, and the role of different management practices were investigated. The study was conducted as part of the EU project REWET (Restoration of Wetlands to minimise emissions and maximise carbon uptake – a strategy for long term climate mitigation). Field measurements were carried out in a floodplain grassland within the Auenreservat Marchegg in eastern Austria during spring 2025. Chamber-based measurements of ecosystem respiration as a proxy for CO₂ flux and CH₄ flux were combined with measurements of soil temperature, soil moisture, and groundwater level along two transects representing grazing and mowing land management. General Additive Models (GAMs) and approaches from Information Theory were applied to quantify the influence of environmental parameters and their interactions on the observed fluxes. At both transects measurements revealed CO₂ emission, i.e. ecosystem respiration (A: $3,37 \pm 1,47 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: $3,11 \pm 2,30 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), and net CH₄ uptake (A: $-0.53 \pm 0.38 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: $-0.34 \pm 0.60 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Episodic CH₄ emissions occurred under elevated soil moisture conditions. Soil temperature revealed the highest impact on CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes in the drier grazed transect A, whereas soil moisture and its interaction with temperature dominated flux dynamics in the wetter, mown transect B. Integrating both CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes into a Global Warming Potential assessment, transect B revealed the smaller GHG footprint. Neither land management type could however be identified as clearly superior, since the measured CO₂ flux excluded plant photosynthesis and the observed differences in CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes between transects appeared to be mainly shaped by site-specific, topographic and hydrological conditions rather than by land management alone.

Kommentiert [AL1]: Einmal auch deutsch:
Zusammenfassung

Kurzfassung

Flussökosysteme wie Auenlandschaften halten im Verhältnis zu ihrer geringen Fläche einen bedeutenden Anteil des globalen Bodenkohlenstoffspeichers. Trotzdem ist ihre Rolle als Nature-Based Climate Solutions bisher nur unzureichend untersucht. Der Einfluss dieser Ökosysteme auf das Klima ist aufgrund der hohen Variabilität von Treibhausgasemissionen unter unterschiedlichen klimatischen Bedingungen schwer zu pauschalisieren. Natürliche Treibhausgase unterliegen komplexen hydrologischen und biogeochemischen Prozessen und werden unter anderem durch Bodentemperatur, Bodenfeuchte und Grundwasser beeinflusst. Insbesondere die, für Auenökosysteme typischen, wechselhaften hydrologischen Bedingungen, wirken sich stark auf die Treibhausgasbilanz aus. Das Trockenfallen von Böden fördert aerobe mikrobielle Stoffwechselprozesse wohingegen ein hoher Bodenwassergehalt anaerobe Bedingungen schaffen kann, welche mit der mikrobiellen Produktion von Methan (CH_4) in Zusammenhang stehen. Um bestehende Wissenslücken zu Auen-Treibhausgasen zu schließen und um nachhaltige Landwirtschaftsmaßnahmen zu entwickeln, wurden Kohlenstoffdioxid (CO_2)- und CH_4 -Flüsse, sowie zugehörige Umweltparameter unterschiedlicher Bewirtschaftungsformen untersucht. Die Studie wurde im Rahmen des EU-Projekts REWET (Restoration of Wetlands to minimise emissions and maximise carbon uptake – a strategy for long term climate mitigation) durchgeführt. Die Feldmessungen im niederösterreichischen Auenreservat Marchegg erfolgten im Frühjahr 2025. Mittels Chamber-Methode wurde der respirative Anteil des CO_2 -Flusses sowie der CH_4 -Fluss entlang zweier Transekte, repräsentativ für die Bewirtschaftungsformen Beweidung und Mahd, gemessen. Zusätzlich wurden Bodentemperatur, Bodenfeuchte und Grundwasserstand erhoben. Zur Untersuchung des Einflusses von Umweltparametern auf die beobachteten Gasflüsse wurden Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) sowie Methoden aus der Information Theory angewandt. An beiden Transekten wurden CO_2 -Emissionen, messbedingt als Ökosystematmung (A: $3,37 \pm 1,47 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: $3,11 \pm 2,30 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) und CH_4 -Abbau (A: $-0,53 \pm 0,38 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: $-0,34 \pm 0,60 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) festgestellt. Episodische CH_4 -Emissionen traten bei hoher Bodenfeuchte auf. Die Bodentemperatur erwies sich im trockeneren, beweideten Transekt A als stärkste Einflussgröße auf die CO_2 - und CH_4 -Flüsse, während die Bodenfeuchte sowie ihre Wechselwirkung mit der Temperatur die Gasflüsse im feuchteren, gemähten Transekt B dominierten. Bei Zusammenfassung der CO_2 - und der CH_4 -Flüsse in die Erhebung des Global Warming Potential (GWP), wies Transekt B den geringeren Treibhausgas-Fußabdruck auf. Jedoch konnte keine der beiden Bewirtschaftungsformen als eindeutig vorteilhaft bestimmt werden, da die gemessenen CO_2 -Flüsse aufgrund der Messtechnik die Photosynthese nicht berücksichtigten und die beobachteten Unterschiede der CO_2 - und CH_4 -Flüsse zwischen den Transekten eher durch standortspezifische topographische und hydrologische Bedingungen und nicht allein durch die Bewirtschaftungsform geprägt zu sein schienen.

Table of Contents

Affidavit	iii
Acknowledgements.....	iv
Abstract.....	v
Kurzfassung	vi
1 Introduction	9
2 Theoretical background to carbon flux dynamics.....	11
2.1 The ecosystem carbon balance	11
2.2 Theory of CO ₂ flux dynamics	12
2.2.1 Sources and production of CO ₂	12
2.2.2 Environmental controls on CO ₂ flux	12
2.3 Theory of CH ₄ flux dynamics	13
2.3.1 Sources and production of CH ₄	13
2.3.2 Environmental controls on CH ₄ Flux.....	14
3 Methodology.....	15
3.1 Site Description	15
3.1.1 Location	15
3.1.2 Soil and vegetation.....	16
3.1.3 Climatic and hydrological conditions	17
3.2 Data Acquisition and Preparation	18
3.2.1 Measurements of CO ₂ and CH ₄ fluxes	18
3.2.2 Measurements of soil moisture and soil temperature	19
3.2.3 Groundwater table – measurement and gap-filling	20
3.3 Statistical Analysis	21
3.3.1 Data preprocessing and visualization.....	21
3.3.2 General additive models (GAM)	21
3.3.3 Information Theory Analysis.....	23
4 Results	24
4.1 Cross-site measurement results.....	24
4.2 Comparison of CO ₂ flux dynamics between transects A & B.....	25
4.2.1 Descriptive statistics of CO ₂ flux.....	25
4.2.2 Environmental parameters: Characteristics and interdependencies	28
4.2.3 GAM analysis of CO ₂ flux and environmental parameters.....	31
4.2.4 Summary of CO ₂ flux dynamics.....	35
4.3 Comparison of CH ₄ flux dynamics between transects A & B.....	36
4.3.1 Descriptive statistics of CH ₄ flux.....	36

4.3.2	Environmental parameters: Characteristics and interdependencies	39
4.3.3	GAM analysis of CH ₄ flux and environmental parameters.....	43
4.3.4	Summary of CH ₄ flux dynamics.....	46
5	Discussion.....	48
5.1	CO ₂ and CH ₄ flux magnitudes in similar literature	48
5.1.1	CO ₂ flux magnitudes	48
5.1.2	CH ₄ flux magnitudes.....	48
5.2	Environmental controls on CO ₂ and CH ₄ flux in the literature	49
5.2.1	Controls of CO ₂ fluxes	49
5.2.2	Controls of CH ₄ fluxes	49
5.3	Implications for land management in the Auenreservat as NCS	50
6	Conclusion	52
7	References	54
	Declaration of the use of generative AI tools	58
	List of Figures.....	59
	List of Tables.....	60
	List of Equations.....	60

1 Introduction

To reach the target of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) Paris Agreement, i.e. holding global warming to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit temperature increase to 1,5°C above pre-industrial levels, a bundle of mitigation measures is necessary (Dybala et al. 2019; Lobus et al. 2023; UNFCCC 2015). However, current policies are insufficient to meet the target (IPCC 2023). According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) the earth is facing a temperature increase of 3,2°C by 2100 (median across ensemble projections), considering the existing mitigation efforts (IPCC 2023). Thus, further climate change mitigation strategies are necessary. Mitigation methods primarily encompass reductions of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions at their source, but are broadened by carbon dioxide removal (CDR) approaches, aiming at capturing and storing already emitted carbon from the atmosphere (Griscom et al. 2017; Lobus et al. 2023). Emission reduction and CDR can be realized through technological, physicochemical processes or through nature-based, biological processes, including hybrid methods that combine both approaches. Nature-based methods, that target conservation, restoration and improved land management of aquatic, terrestrial and transitional ecosystems are distinguished as Nature Climate Solutions (NCS) (Ellis et al. 2024; Griscom et al. 2017). Among NCS, reductions of future emissions are realized through improving land management practices and through inhibiting land use change. NCS for carbon capture and storage rely on the capacity of vegetation and soil to assimilate and sequester carbon (Altor und Mitsch 2008; Dybala et al. 2019; Hansen et al. 2017). Besides climate change mitigation, NCS can provide co-benefits such as biodiversity conservation, improvement of hydrological and nutrient cycle and general ecosystem resilience (Dybala et al. 2019; Griscom et al. 2017; IPCC 2023). Estimates suggest that NCS could contribute up to 23,8 Pg CO₂e yr⁻¹ by 2030, representing approximately one-third of the mitigation required to meet climate targets (Ellis et al. 2024; Griscom et al. 2017).

To enable an effective implementation of NCS, comprehensive greenhouse gas flux data of various ecosystems is required. In this context, wetlands constitute an exceptional role, as they store 20-30% of the global soil carbon pool while only covering 5-8% of the terrestrial surface (Batson et al. 2015; Mitsch et al. 2013). The special position of wetlands regarding climate change mitigation stems from their increased plant productivity, enabling the incorporation of CO₂ into organic matter and the formation of stable organic compounds in hydric soils (Gong et al. 2024; Mitsch et al. 2013; Were et al. 2019). Among wetlands, riparian ecosystems such as floodplain forests and grasslands remain relatively poor studied, but could constitute valuable climate change mitigation assets (Acosta et al. 2017; Dybala et al. 2019; Gong et al. 2024; Jacinthe 2015; Schindlbacher et al. 2022).

Regarding the climate change impact of riparian ecosystems, fluctuating hydrological conditions represent a key controlling factor. Periodic flooding and associated changes in groundwater levels affect plants and soil organisms, which in turn shape carbon and nitrogen balances (Altor und Mitsch 2008; Gong et al. 2024; Schindlbacher et al. 2022). Hydric soil conditions can suppress soil-microbial respiration, thereby reducing CO₂ production (Altor und Mitsch 2008; Gong et al. 2024), but can also trigger emissions of GHG methane (CH₄) (Jacinthe 2015; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Were et al. 2019) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) (Gebremichael et al. 2017; Schindlbacher et al. 2022). When assessing the net climate change effect of riparian ecosystems, the balance between CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes needs to be carefully evaluated.

To close the existing information gaps on GHG dynamics of riparian ecosystems, detailed data on riparian gas fluxes and controlling environmental parameters like soil moisture, groundwater level etc. are required. To help address these gaps, this study contributes to the research of the

Kommentiert [MV2]: Tolle Einleitung!

Du beschreibst hier auch das Research gap und dann ist es auch wichtig zu zeigen, wie deine Arbeit hilft diese GAP zu füllen und mit welchen Forschungsfragen du dieses Thema bearbeitest...

Kommentiert [DB3R2]: Habe jetzt ein paar Zeilen weiter den Beitrag unserer Arbeit zu Kunos GHG Flux Datenbank erwähnt und die Forschungsfragen als Ziele aufgelistet. Hoffe das passt besser!

EU project REWET (Restoration of Wetlands to minimise emissions and maximise carbon uptake – a strategy for long term climate mitigation), which is analysing GHG flux data of 7 wetlands across Europe, representing different climatic and ecological conditions. Specifically, this thesis supplies GHG and correlating environmental data from an Austrian riparian wetland to a European-wide GHG flux database. The general ambition of REWET is to minimize emissions and maximize carbon uptake, by developing restoration and land management strategies. In line with these targets, this thesis aims to examine the wetland's GHG sink or source behaviour, investigate relationships between controlling environmental parameters and GHG fluxes and identify potential land management implications to reduce the site's climate impact.

The study site is located in the Auenreservat Marchegg along the Morava River in eastern Austria and comprises floodplain grassland within a floodplain forest. During the springtime of 2025, CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O fluxes were measured simultaneously with soil temperature, soil moisture and groundwater level. Subsequently, CO₂ and CH₄ flux characteristics and their relationships with environmental parameters were investigated. N₂O fluxes are being evaluated and analysed simultaneously in a companion study. Moreover, the climate impact of two sites with different land management practices is compared. One study site is managed through mechanical mowing, while the other is grazed by Konik horses and cattle.

Statistical analyses conducted to address the research targets are based on General Additive Modelling (GAM) and Information Theory approaches. Through model development and the evaluation of individual parameter contribution to the model performance, as well as nonlinear correlation analysis, this study aims to discover non-linear relationships and variable interdependencies in ecosystem's GHG fluxes. The findings are intended to support the development of sustainable management strategies for riparian and wetland areas in the context of climate change mitigation.

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows: Section 2 gives theoretical background information on the sources, production and environmental controls of carbon fluxes. Section 3 describes the study area and the study's methodology. Section 4 presents the results of the flux measurements and the statistical analyses, while section 5 discusses the findings in the context of existing literature and their implications for land management and climate change mitigation. Finally, section 6 summarizes the main conclusions and outlines improvements and further objectives for future **research** in riparian ecosystem like the Auenreservat Marchegg.

Kommentiert [AL4]: Konkrete Forschungsfragen?

Kommentiert [DB5R4]: Es handelt sich bei Section 5 vor allem um Verbesserungsvorschläge zur Beantwortung der bestehenden Forschungsfragen. Habe den Satz dementsprechend angepasst.

Kommentiert [MV6]: Nach der Introduction solltest du noch ein Kapitel 2 - Theoretical Background machen und da alle basis infos von euren Recherchen zum Carbon cycle etc. rein geben!

2 Theoretical background to carbon flux dynamics

2.1 The ecosystem carbon balance

Carbon fluxes in natural systems, like riparian forests, grass- or wetlands can be distinguished into autochthonous fluxes and allochthonous fluxes (Were et al. 2019). Autochthonous fluxes comprise atmosphere-ecosystem interactions based on the ecosystem's own carbon pool (Methanogenesis, Methanotrophy, Respiration and Photosynthesis in Figure 11), allochthonous fluxes describe carbon exchange with external sources (C in- and outflow in Figure 11). Carbon that is decomposed and buried in the soil can be regarded as addition to the long-term carbon stock (Death, Decomposition and C Burial in Figure 11). Carbon can be transported in gaseous, particulate, or dissolved forms (Bergamaschi

et al. 2010; Were et al. 2019), with this study focusing on gaseous exchange of the two primary carbon greenhouse gases CO₂ and CH₄.

Figure 1: Carbon balance of the study's floodplain. Photograph by author; overlay graphics and text rendering generated with the assistance of Google Gemini (May 2026), adapted from the conceptual framework in "Fig.1 Simplified schematic overview of C cycling in wetlands" by Were et al. (2019, p. 329).

2.2 Theory of CO₂ flux dynamics

2.2.1 Sources and production of CO₂

CO₂ is created from organic matter under aerobic, well oxygenated conditions (**Figure 1**). Regarding the CO₂ balance between an ecosystem and its atmosphere, CO₂ is either taken up, primarily by plant photosynthesis, or CO₂ is produced by respiration, decomposition and combustion of organic material (Bergamaschi et al. 2010; Paustian et al. 2006; Were et al. 2019). At the ecosystem level, respiration encompasses autotrophic respiration, representing the metabolism of living plant cells and heterotrophic respiration, representing the microbial decomposition of soil organic matter (**Figure 1**) (Reichstein et al. 2005). Heterotrophic respiration

is the main pathway through which soil carbon is oxidised and returned to the atmosphere as CO₂, with soil microorganisms utilising organic matter as an energy and carbon source (Paustian et al. 2006). Furthermore, plant roots supply organic compounds, like sugars and organic acids, to the rhizosphere, fostering microbial activity and thereby indirectly increasing heterotrophic CO₂ production (Were et al. 2019). Together, autotrophic and heterotrophic respiration constitute the ecosystem respiration (R_{eco}) (**Figure 1**). The total CO₂ flux balance of an ecosystem can be quantified by the parameter of net ecosystem exchange (NEE) (

Equation 1). NEE is the result of opposing ecosystem respiration (R_{eco}) and the term of Gross Ecosystem Production (GEP) (Nadolski et al. 2025; Reichstein et al. 2005). R_{eco} is comprising the CO₂ flux of all respiring ecosystem compounds, primarily soil and vegetation, whereas GEP is describing CO₂ uptake by photosynthesis prior to subtracting plant respiration losses. A positive NEE indicates CO₂ release, whereas a negative value reflects CO₂ uptake, thereby characterizing the ecosystem as a carbon source or sink.

$$NEE = R_{eco} - GEP$$

Equation 1: Formula for Net Ecosystem Exchange (NEE).

2.2.2 Environmental controls on CO₂ flux

Ecosystem CO₂ flux is influenced by a combination of physical, chemical, biological and vegetation-related factors. Since NEE results from opposing R_{eco} and GEP, environmental parameters influence CO₂ flux both by modifying respiration rates and by altering the photosynthetic activity of vegetation (Nadolski et al. 2025; Reichstein et al. 2005). R_{eco} is mainly determined by the environmental conditions affecting microbial and root metabolic activity, with soil temperature and soil moisture emerging as the dominant environmental parameters across a wide range of terrestrial ecosystem types (Acosta et al. 2017; Batson et al. 2015; Gong et al. 2024; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Walkiewicz et al. 2025). GEP and thereby CO₂ assimilation depend on vegetation properties, like plant species composition, above ground biomass or plant height (Darenova et al. 2016; Nadolski et al. 2025). Vegetation parameters influencing GEP however depend again on water, solar radiation and temperature related variables (Nadolski et al. 2025).

Soil temperature exerts a positive influence on R_{eco} by fostering the metabolic rates of both soil microorganisms and plant roots. The temperature sensitivity of soil respiration can be described by the Q10 coefficient, expressing the increase in respiration per 10°C temperature rise. Across forest, grassland and cropland ecosystems, Q10 values for CO₂ respiration typically range between 1,3 and 2,8, although this sensitivity tends to decline at higher temperatures (Walkiewicz et al. 2025). The relationship between temperature and CO₂ flux however is not independent of soil water conditions. Concurrent high soil moisture can modify the CO₂ flux by suppressing microbial activity and by inhibiting physical transport of CO₂ through the soil pore system (Darenova et al. 2016).

Soil moisture influences CO₂ production in a more complex manner. Under conditions of low to moderate soil moisture, aerobic decomposition is sustained and microbial CO₂ production increases with soil warming. Under these conditions soil moisture can even increase CO₂ production by diffusing substrates and increasing the availability of dissolved organic carbon to decomposers (Hao et al. 2025; Huang und Hall 2017) However, when soil moisture reaches a critical threshold and the water-filled pore space increases substantially, oxygen diffusion is inhibited, suppressing aerobic microbial activity and thereby reducing CO₂ production. A

moisture threshold effect is especially pronounced in riparian systems with high hydrological connectivity (Acosta et al. 2017; Batson et al. 2015; Schindlbacher et al. 2022).

Vegetation simultaneously influences GEP through photosynthetic CO₂ assimilation and contributes to R_{eco} through autotrophic plant respiration. CO₂ uptake rates of forest ecosystems in Finland and Sweden were in a similar magnitude as concurrent R_{eco} rates (Lankreijer et al. 2009). Among vegetation parameters, aboveground biomass was identified as a significant driver of CO₂ flux in grassland and wetland ecosystems, as greater biomass fosters photosynthetic activity and simultaneously increases organic matter inputs into the soil (Darenova et al. 2016; Gong et al. 2024). Furthermore, forest type and vegetation cover affect soil CO₂ dynamics by regulating the light availability at the soil surface, thereby controlling the balance between photosynthesis and respiration (Walkiewicz et al. 2025).

2.3 Theory of CH₄ flux dynamics

2.3.1 Sources and production of CH₄

The CH₄ flux of an ecosystem can be distinguished into methanogenesis (CH₄ production) and methanotrophy (CH₄ consumption) (**Figure 1**) (Conrad 2009). CH₄ fluxes at ecosystem level are primarily driven by microbial processes and, to a much lesser extent, by incomplete biomass burning (Conrad 2009; Paustian et al. 2006). Microbially driven CH₄ fluxes result from a complex interplay of hydrogeological and biogeochemical processes as well as vegetation influences. Whether CH₄ is taken up or released is determined by the opposing processes of methanogenesis and methanotrophy, occurring under contrasting redox conditions within the soil profile (Conrad 2009). Methanogenesis is carried out by methanogenic archaea and represents the final phase of anaerobic degradation of organic matter. The process requires strongly reducing conditions, which are established once other electron acceptors, like molecular oxygen (O₂) or nitrate (NO₃⁻) have been consumed (Conrad 2009). Under such conditions, methanogens use CO₂ and simple organic compounds, such as acetate and formate, as energy source producing CH₄ as metabolic byproduct. In natural systems, methanogenesis mostly appears in permanently or periodically waterlogged soils, where long term anaerobic conditions maintain CH₄ production (**Figure 1**) (Conrad 2009; Schindlbacher et al. 2022). The widespread assumption that CH₄ emissions can only occur under waterlogged, fully anaerobic conditions has been challenged, leading to scientific disagreement over the exact nature of CH₄ production (Angle et al. 2017; Conrad 2009). Nevertheless, there is broad consensus that CH₄ emissions are closely linked to high soil moisture levels. Increased CH₄ emissions are triggered by flooding events or minor fluctuations in the groundwater table (Buzacott et al. 2024; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Were et al. 2019).

Microbial methanotrophy appears in oxygenized, usually upper layers of the soil and plant tissue (**Figure 1**) (Buzacott et al. 2024; Were et al. 2019). Aerobic methanotrophs utilise CH₄ as their only carbon and energy source, oxidising it to CO₂ and water. In well-aerated soils, often in the aerobic surface layers of riparian and wetland soils, methanotrophic activity can offset methanogenesis from deeper soil layers, such that many temperate soils act as net atmospheric CH₄ sinks (Conrad 2009; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Walkiewicz et al. 2025). Whether a soil functions as a net CH₄ source or sink is therefore determined by the balance between methanogenesis in deeper anaerobic soil layers and methanotrophy in higher aerobic horizons (**Figure 1**) (Buzacott et al. 2024; Were et al. 2019).

2.3.2 Environmental controls on CH₄ Flux

The balance between methanogenesis and methanotrophy is determined by different abiotic and biotic factors, among which soil moisture exerts the main impact (Batson et al. 2015; Jacinthe 2015; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Walkiewicz et al. 2025). Soil moisture affects CH₄ flux primarily

through its control over soil redox conditions and O₂ availability. As soil moisture increases, aerobic pore space is eliminated, which is suppressing methanotrophic activity. Once anoxic conditions are established, methanogenesis takes place. Accordingly, sudden increases in soil moisture during precipitation or flood events have been consistently associated with peak CH₄ emissions across diverse riparian and wetland ecosystems (Batson et al. 2015; Gong et al. 2024; Schindlbacher et al. 2022). The degree to which flooding or precipitation events cause CH₄ emission depends on site-specific soil and vegetation parameters that either foster waterlogging or facilitate rapid drainage (Schindlbacher et al. 2022). In this context, soil represents a significant soil parameter. Fine-textured soils with high clay content retain more water, limit O₂ diffusion and thereby favour methanogenesis, whereas coarser, sandy soils promote aeration and support microbial methanotrophy (Batson et al. 2015; Jacinthe 2015).

The role of soil temperature in affecting CH₄ fluxes is more complex and context-dependent than for CO₂. Higher soil temperatures can foster both methanotrophic and methanogenic microbial activity, but their respective activation depends on soil moisture (Jacinthe 2015). Under warm and dry conditions, increasing temperature enhances methanotrophy, as aerobic conditions are maintained and enzymatic activity increases with warmth (Walkiewicz et al. 2025). Similarly, higher temperatures stimulate methanogenic archaea under waterlogged conditions, promoting increased CH₄ methanogenesis (Buzacott et al. 2024). Thus, the interaction between soil temperature and soil moisture determines the direction and magnitude of the temperature effect on CH₄ flux (Jacinthe 2015).

Besides soil moisture and soil temperature, ammonium (NH₄⁺) has been shown to competitively inhibit methanotrophic enzymes, thereby reducing methanotrophy when NH₄⁺ concentrations are high (Batson et al. 2015; Gong et al. 2024; Walkiewicz et al. 2025). Soil pH influences the activity of both methanogenic archaea and methanotrophic bacteria, as both microbial communities have distinct pH optima, with deviations from near-neutral conditions reducing the respective metabolic rates (Gong et al. 2024). Finally, soil organic carbon content provides the substrate for methanogenesis under anaerobic conditions. Higher soil organic contents are associated with increased CH₄ production potential in waterlogged soils (Walkiewicz et al. 2025).

3 Methodology

3.1 Site Description

3.1.1 Location

The study site lies within the nature reserve "Untere March-Auen" also referred to as "Auenreservat Marchegg", encompassing near-natural floodplain forests and meadow areas. It is situated in eastern Lower Austria along the Morava River (**Figure 32**) between the communities of Zwerndorf and Marchegg. The reserve is a core part of the Europe- and Ramsar-protected river system "March-Thaya Auen" and covers approximately 1.100 hectares (Westerhof et al. 2024). The area is partly owned by the Worldwide Fund for Nature (WWF) Austria and a private family and is represented by the "Forstverwaltung Marchauen".

Figure 2: Location of the study site in Eastern Austria, Source: Location of the study site at the border of Austria and Slovakia in the nature reserve near Marchegg, Lower Austria. Lindenberger et al (2025, p.2).

Since 2015, scientists examine the grazing effect of large herbivores on the reserve's vegetation and landscape diversity. Therefore, a herd of 20 Konik horses (Status 2024) roam an area of approximately 80 hectares. Moreover cattle owned by a local farmer are seasonally introduced to graze on plant species rejected by the horses (Westerhof et al. 2024). Within that grazed area lies an Eddy Covariance (EC) research station run by the project REWET (red dot in **Figure 2**). Access to the site was granted by the Forstverwaltung Marchauen with legalisation by the nature conservation department of the province of Lower Austria.

To assess the impact of grazing and mowing land management on soil carbon fluxes, two sites within the Auenreservat Marchegg are examined. These sites are referred to as transect A and transect B. Transect A lies within the grazing paddock, close to the EC station and consists of 9 measuring points named A1-A9 (**Figure 3**). The transect crosses a former oxbow of the Morava River, visible on the map in beige and lighter shades of green. The oxbow is periodically flooded in high flow periods. Measuring points A4-A6 lie within the oxbow bed, while measuring points A1-

A3 as well as A7-A9 are situated higher up on grassland. Transect B is located approximately 1 km away in a meadow outside the grazing area, which is mechanically mown twice a year (**Figure 3**). It encompasses 5 measuring points named B1-B5 and spans from a group of trees (B1-B3) situated higher up, to a low-lying marshy depression (B4-B5), which is occasionally water covered.

Figure 3: Location of transect A&B within the Auenreservat Marchegg.

3.1.2 Soil and vegetation

According to the Soil Map of Austria (<https://bodenkarte.at/>, accessed 16.02.2026), run by the Austrian Federal Research and Training Centre for Forests, Natural Hazards and Landscape, the soil type at both transect A and transect B can be described as grey, gley soil of fine alluvial material. The soil profile encompasses a humus-rich topsoil layer, succeeded by a loamy, clayey layer and a coarse gravel layer starting at the depth of one meter. The soil is significantly affected by fluctuating groundwater level. Low estival groundwater levels alternate with periodical surface water stagnation, particularly during snowmelt season, heavy rain, or backflow events from the Danube. To obtain higher detail on soil properties, samples were taken at measuring points A2, A6, A8, B1 and B4 in two depths between 0–20 cm and 20–40 cm beneath soil surface. The samples were then examined in the laboratory for soil texture, carbon and nitrogen content, C/N ratio and pH value. Especially the soil carbon content is fundamental for the analysis of an ecosystem's CO₂ and CH₄ dynamics (Jacinthe 2015; Metcalfe et al. 2007; Schindlbacher et al. 2022). The results of the soil analysis can be found in section 4.1.

Above ground biotope types of Auenreservat Marchegg range from frequently flooded soft wood forests and sedge-reed marshes to alluvial meadows, semi-arid grasslands and oak-dominated hard wood forests. The surrounding of transect A can be described as a meadow on alluvial soil, dominated by herbaceous and shrubby vegetation. Transect B partly encompasses a meadow overgrown by large grasses and a marshy depression covered by helophytes in direct proximity of a hardwood floodplain forest. The vegetation in both transects A and B grew over the progressing study period (Figure 4 4). Transect B was mown during the week between the 10.06.2025 and the 17.06.2025, however the vegetation within the measuring collars was not affected.

Figure 4: Vegetation changes in transect A and B over the study period.

3.1.3 Climatic and hydrological conditions

The climate in eastern Lower Austria can be described as Pannonian, which is a continental climate with pronounced seasonal temperature contrasts characterized by hot, dry summers, and cold winters (Nagl 2004). The mean multi-annual temperature from 1997 to 2025, recorded at the closest weather station to Auenreservat Marchegg in Zwerndorf, was 10,6°C. With a relatively low multi-annual mean precipitation of 548 mm, this area ranks among the regions with lowest rainfall in Austria. Meteorological data was accessed via the website of Geosphere Austria, the federal Institute for Geology, Geophysics, Climatology and Meteorology

(<https://dataset.api.hub.geosphere.at/app/frontend/station/historical/klima-v2-1y>, accessed 18.03.2026).

The study site's hydrogeological conditions are dominated by the flow conditions of Morava River. The river was channelised and detached from oxbows and tributaries during the 20th century, leading to a channel bed deepening of 1,5m and a strong reduction of lateral connectivity (Lindenberger et al. 2025). For flood protection purposes, the Auenreservat Marchegg is intersected by the flood protection dike of the community of Marchegg. Both transect A and transect B lie between Morava River and the dike and are thereby directly connected to the main channel during flood events. Especially the former oxbow, forming a topographic flowpath within the floodplain, is regularly flooded during high flow. The surface water depth during flooding reaches 15 cm on average every year, 38 cm every 2 years and 138 cm every 30 years. After the floods recede, water remains in local depressions forming shallow water bodies (Lindenberger et al. 2025).

3.2 Data Acquisition and Preparation

3.2.1 Measurement of CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes

In this study, gaseous CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes were measured at the soil surface using the Chamber Method (CM). This method is based on three instrument components: measuring collars installed in the ground (**Figure 6**), a measuring chamber (**Figure 5**), and the measuring device LI-7810 Trace Gas Analyzer by LI-COR (**Figure 5**). Information about the LI-7810 device can be found on the website of LI-COR (<https://www.licor.com/products/trace-gas/LI-7810>, accessed 23.03.2026). The collars were installed at an approximate soil depth of 15 cm, one week before the first flux measurement to allow the soil to settle (**Figure 66**). Each collar is equipped with a groove along its upper edge that can be filled with water to ensure an airtight seal when the measuring chamber is applied. The measuring chamber is airtight and designed to capture all air emitted from the soil within the collar. The inside of the chamber contains a small ventilator fan to ensure air circulation, as well as a thermo- and a hygrometer. The chamber is connected to the LI-7810 Trace Gas Analyzer via tubes. During the measurement, captured air is fed into the LI-7810 device, where it is analysed for CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations using infrared absorption spectroscopy. Infrared light emitted by the device is transmitted through the sampled air, where each gas absorbs the light at characteristic wavelengths. The amount of absorbed light is proportional to the amount of CO₂ or CH₄ in the air, enabling direct concentration measurements of CO₂ in ppm and CH₄ in ppb. A single measurement takes 5 minutes, during which gas concentrations are measured continuously. The LI-7810 device features wireless data transmission, allowing real time control of the measurements in the field. By analysing the change in the concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄ within the chamber over the measurement time and considering the surface within one collar, fluxes can be calculated. Using the ideal gas law, concentration units (ppm and ppb) can be converted into flux units $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\text{nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively.

Kommentiert [AL7]: Mir ist der ganze theoretische Hintergrund zu CH₄ und CO₂ etwas zu wenig? Extra kapitel dazu? Und dann hier nur measurement methodology of chambers?

Figure 5: Measurement Chamber (left) and Licor LI-7810 device (right).

Since the measuring chamber is opaque, photosynthesis is inhibited during the measurement. Obtained CO₂ flux values therefore correspond to the R_{eco} term of the NEE equation and do not describe the complete ecosystem's CO₂ balance (Equation 1).

The measured R_{eco} can further be separated into its components soil and plant respiration. This was realized by installing a second collar (B2NPC – No Plant Cover) next to measurement point B2 and removing all the plant cover at ring B2NPC. CO₂ flux measurements at B2NPC reflect soil respiration alone, whereas B2 measurements capture the combined effect of both plant and soil respiration.

The study's data collection took place between the 07.04.2025 and the 23.06.2025. Transect B however was implemented three weeks later than transect A causing an offset of measurement periods. Transect B's measurements were therefore conducted between the 29.04.2025 and the 23.06.2025. For analysis that required direct comparison, the measurement period of transect A was restricted to match that of transect B. The collar B2NPC was installed prior to the 10.06.2025, resulting in three B2NPC measurement days on the 10.06.2025, the 17.06.2025 and the 23.06.2025.

3.2.2 Measurement of soil moisture and soil temperature

To assess environmental conditions relevant to carbon gas flux dynamics, soil moisture and soil temperature were recorded at all measuring points simultaneously with the gas flux measurements. The measurements were conducted using TMS-4 dataloggers developed by TOMST (<https://tomst.com/web/en/systems/tms/tms-4/>, accessed 23.03.2026), that measure both soil temperature and soil moisture. Each device consists of a measurement lance, which is inserted into the soil, and a datalogger unit (**Figure 6**). The TMS-4 moisture sensor is based on an indirect electrical measurement, sending electro-magnetic impulses through the lance and measuring the number of returned signals per defined time unit (Jačka et al. 2023). This number is dependent on the soil's dielectric constant which can be used as a proxy for soil water content. Since the dielectric constant is not solely dependent on soil moisture, but also on soil properties, the TMS-4 sensors must be calibrated based on soil samples for transect A and B respectively. Soil samples were collected in the field, oven-dried in the laboratory and equipped with a TOMST TMS-4 device. To set up a calibration function, the samples were then saturated in a stepwise manner. Since the amount of water added, and the soil volume are known, the volumetric water

content at each saturation level can be calculated. Simultaneously, the TOMST TMS-4 is measuring soil water content as well in the form of raw TMS-4 values, which reflect the number of returned electric impulses and therefore must be converted into volumetric water content (Jačka et al. 2023). By pairing the calculated volumetric water content with the corresponding TMS-4 measurements at each saturation step, a transfer function can be derived that integrates both calibration and conversion into a single calculation. For both transect A and B one transfer function was developed, that considers site-specific corrections and allows for TMS-4 output to be converted into volumetric water content (Jačka et al. 2023).

Figure 6: TOMST TMS-4 (left) next to collar (right).

3.2.3 Groundwater table – measurement and gap-filling

To obtain additional hydrological context to carbon flux data, a piezometer was installed at the REWET project's research station, recording hourly groundwater levels throughout the measurement period. The piezometer was constructed from a perforated PVC tube wrapped in geotextile, which is implemented into a borehole and contains two HOBO Water Level Loggers U20L-04 (<https://www.onsetcomp.com/products/data-loggers/u20l-0x>, accessed 23.03.2026). One of the sensors is installed at the bottom of the tube and measures the height of the water column above it. The other sensor is located above the groundwater level and measures atmospheric pressure to compensate for the effect of air pressure changes on the water level measurements. However, due to an insufficient depth of the piezometer borehole, the HOBO device ran dry, resulting in a data gap between the 02.05.25 and the 23.06.2025. Missing values were gap-filled using an ARIMAX model (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average with exogenous variables) built on external groundwater and precipitation data. Transfer function models, which is the precursor of ARIMAX models, are widely used tools for the prediction of hydrological time series. These approaches combine the internal temporal structure of the target variable with the influence of external variables such as precipitation or external groundwater observations (Asmuth et al. 2008; Salas et al. 1980). For comparison, a multivariate regression model using the same input variables was established. The ARIMAX model, however, achieved better predictive performance, as demonstrated by lower root mean square error (RMSE) and mean average error (MAE) values. The ARIMAX model was set up in R – software based on the “forecast” package (Hyndman et al. 2009). The external groundwater data used in the ARIMAX model were obtained from a well located in Baumgarten an der March (331769), while precipitation data were sourced from weather station Salmhof (116426). Both stations are operated by the Hydrographic Service of Lower Austria (<https://ehyd.gv.at/>, accessed 25.03.2025). Of the three monitoring wells situated around the Auenreservat Marchegg, only one

was implemented into the ARIMAX model, due to low correlation between the in-situ piezometer data and the other station's observations. The low correlation between groundwater wells may reflect the separation of groundwater bodies by the Marchegg flood-protection levee. Due to the reduced reliability of gap-filled groundwater data and the limited explanatory power of groundwater levels for carbon gas fluxes in transect A, groundwater data were used only for visual correlation analysis and were not included in the statistical analysis.

3.3 Statistical Analysis

3.3.1 Data preprocessing and visualization

After calibration and unit conversion, all measurement data were integrated into a unified database. Data processing and analysis were conducted in R (version 4.5.3, R Core Team) using RStudio 2025.09.02 (<https://www.r-project.org/>, accessed 04.04.2026). The dataset was cleaned by removing incomplete observations to ensure consistency across all variables. For analyses requiring direct comparison between transects A and B, the observation period was adapted to the overlapping measurement period (29.04.2025-23.06.2025).

Initial exploration of the data was performed through calculation of descriptive statistics, i.e. mean values, standard deviance and range values of CO₂ and CH₄ flux as well as environmental parameters. In a second step, CO₂, CH₄ fluxes and environmental parameters were plotted over time and across the transect to provide a preliminary assessment of trends, temporal and spatial variability, and potential relationships between variables. The visualisations were used as a guide for the choice and interpretation of the following methods. Prior to statistical analysis, a dependency between the two environmental predictors soil temperature and soil moisture was identified. In linear models this is referred to as collinearity, and in the non-linear context of GAMs as concurvity (Wood 2017). Since the two variables share overlapping information, they cannot be treated as independent predictors. This will be accounted for in the statistical analysis.

3.3.2 General additive models (GAM)

To investigate the correlations between CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes and environmental parameters, General Additive Models (GAMs) were set up in R using the package "mgcv" (Wood 2025b). These models can be used for predicting a target variable based on multiple parameters, but also for evaluating the explanatory power of the model predictors and their interaction (Lai et al. 2024; Wood 2017). GAMs can model different kind of variable distributions, like Poisson- or log-distribution. For the case of carbon gas fluxes, a Gaussian distribution of values can be assumed. GAMs extend generalized linear models by assessing the relationship between the target variable Y and predictors x using smooth terms f_i for each predictor (Equation 2). Smooth terms are additive functions built on a combination of basis-functions b_i (Equation 3), whose coefficients β_i are estimated during model fitting and are subject to a smoothness penalty that controls the degree of smooth function wiggleness (Hastie und Tibshirani 1986; Wood 2017, 2025a). Since additive functions tend to create highly complex superpositions of basis-functions, complexity captured by smooth wiggleness must be kept at minimum. Interaction effects that cannot be represented by single predictors can be implemented in the model using tensor product smooths combining multiple predictors (Equation 4). The statistical significance of smooth terms is performed by p-value based Wald-Tests (Wood 2025b).

$$E(Y) = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^i f_i(x_i) = \beta_0 + f_1(x_1) + f_2(x_2) + \dots + f_i(x_i)$$

Equation 2: Structure of GAM for a Gaussian distribution of Y : ($E(Y)$ = expectancy value of Y , x_i = predictor, β_0 = intercept, f_i = smooth term).

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^i \beta_i b_i(x)$$

Equation 3: Smooth term function in GAM (β_i = weights, b_i = basis function).

$$f(x, z) = \sum_{i=1}^{k_x} \sum_{j=1}^{k_z} \beta_{ij} \cdot b_i(x) \cdot b_j(z)$$

Equation 4: Tensor function in GAM (x, z = predictors).

In this study, separate GAMs with CO_2 and CH_4 flux as targets were fitted, each including smooth terms for soil temperature and soil moisture alongside a tensor product smooth to capture the interactive effect of soil temperature and soil moisture. The capacity to detect both linear and non-linear relationships as well as interactive effects makes GAMs a widely used tool for analysing complex ecological processes like ecosystem greenhouse gas fluxes (Jensen et al. 2023; Webb et al. 2019; Wiik et al. 2018). The concavity between soil temperature and soil moisture, identified prior to model fitting, can be quantified within the model using the GAM concavity index. This index measures the degree to which one smooth term can be approximated by a combination of other smooth terms in the model, with values approaching 1 indicating near-complete redundancy of information (Wood 2017). The model performance was assessed using deviance explained (D^2), which quantifies the proportion of null deviance explained by the fitted model and is equivalent to R^2 under the assumption of normally distributed residuals (Wood, 2017; Lai et al., 2024). The explanatory power of predictor variables can be assessed by D^2 partitioning. This method is performed by sequentially adding variables to a GAM (Equation 5) and tracking the corresponding change in D^2 to quantify the contributions of each predictor and their interaction to the overall D^2 (Lai et al. 2024; Randin et al. 2009).

$$\text{Model 1: } \text{CO}_2 \sim s(\text{ST})$$

$$\text{Model 2: } \text{CO}_2 \sim s(\text{SM})$$

$$\text{Model 3: } \text{CO}_2 \sim s(\text{ST}) + s(\text{SM})$$

$$\text{Model 4: } \text{CO}_2 \sim s(\text{ST}) + s(\text{SM}) + ti(\text{ST}, \text{SM})$$

Equation 5: Model structure of D^2 partitioning for CO_2 flux based on smooth terms (s) for soil temperature (ST), soil moisture (SM) and interaction tensor (ti).

The additional information added by a predictor, when the other predictor is already implemented into the model is called unique D^2 and is calculated by subtracting individual D^2 from shared D^2 values (Equation 6). Individual and unique D^2 metrics enable the identification of dominant environmental parameters and separation of shared versus independent effects (Lai et al. 2024).

$$D^2_{\text{unique}} = D^2_{\text{ST+SM}} - D^2_{\text{ST}}$$

Equation 6: Calculation of unique D^2 for the example of soil moisture (SM).

GAM results were visualized using two complementary approaches. Individual smooth terms were visualized as partial effect plots, displaying the estimated smooth function of each predictor on CO_2 and CH_4 flux respectively (Figure 18, Figure 20, Figure 33, Figure 35). The partial effect

plots further contain confidence intervals indicating estimation uncertainty of smooth term effects. Contour plots were used to display CO₂ and CH₄ flux as isolines across the two-dimensional predictor space of soil temperature and soil moisture, thereby revealing interactive flux hotspots (**Figure 19, Figure 21, Figure 34, Figure 36**).

3.3.3 Information Theory Analysis

To validate the observations about flux-parameter relationships obtained by the GAMs, Mutual Information (MI) from Information Theory was applied. This non-parametric measure is capable of detecting both linear and non-linear relationships between environmental variables (Ruddell und Kumar 2009; Sturtevant et al. 2016). MI quantifies the mutual information content between two variables and is based on the concept of Shannon entropy H (Ruddell und Kumar 2009; Shannon 1948). Shannon entropy describes the abundance of information within a variable and is calculated based on the variable's probability distribution $p(y)$ (**Equation 7**). The reduction of information abundance $H(Y)$ within the target variable Y , when considering a second variable X is called Mutual Information (**Equation 8**) (Knox et al. 2018; Nadolski et al. 2025; Ruddell und Kumar 2009; Sturtevant et al. 2016).

$$H(Y) = - \sum_y p(y) \ln(p(y))$$

Equation 7: Calculation of Shannon Entropy.

$$MI(X; Y) = H(Y) - H(Y | X)$$

Equation 8: Calculation of Mutual Information.

To enable comparability across variables, MI can be normalized by the overall entropy of the target variable Y to yield Relative Mutual Information (RMI) (Knox et al. 2018; Sturtevant et al. 2016), which ranges from 0 to 1, where values approaching 1 indicate a strong explanatory relationship and values approaching 0 indicate independence between variables (**Equation 9**).

$$RMI = \frac{MI(X; Y)}{H(Y)}$$

Equation 9: Calculation of Relative Mutual Information.

All calculations concerning MI were performed in R using the package “infotheo” (Meyer 2022). Prior to MI analysis, the observation data had to be discretized into bins representing segments of the data probability distribution (Nadolski et al. 2025; Ruddell und Kumar 2009; Sturtevant et al. 2016). To define the optimal bin number, MI values were calculated for a rising number of bins. Since MI values are positively biased by bin number (Ruddell und Kumar 2009; Sturtevant et al. 2016), the noise contribution associated with each bin number was estimated from 500 shuffled surrogate datasets and subtracted from the MI values. The optimal bin number is reached at the onset of a stable plateau in MI values, before noise contributions begin to overwhelm the mutual information signal (Ruddell und Kumar 2009). Statistical significance of MI and RMI values was assessed using the Shuffled Surrogate approach (Ruddell und Kumar 2009).

RMI values were obtained between each flux and environmental parameters soil temperature and soil moisture respectively. Coupled Mutual Information (CMI), an extended information-theoretic metric accounting for collinearity (Wood 2025b) between soil temperature and soil moisture, was calculated, but excluded from further analysis due to statistical insignificance in Shuffled Surrogate testing. Although RMI results capture only the relationship between a single

environmental parameter and a single flux at a time, they still provide a useful basis for the comparison with the relationships discovered by the GAM analysis.

4 Results

4.1 Cross-site measurement results

The results of the soil sampling and laboratory analysis are plotted below (**Table 1**). Based on the measured concentrations of sand, silt and clay and using the Austrian texture triangle (ÖNORM L1050), the soil at all sampled points (A2, A6, A8, B1, B4) was categorized as loamy clay (Schwarz et al. 2022). None of the samples contained any inorganic carbon, consequently the organic carbon fraction corresponds to the total carbon content (C_{tot}). Since the variation of C_{tot} between measuring points of the same transect was small, an average value for each transect at each of the two sampled soil depths was calculated. The upper layer of transect A (0-20 cm) revealed an average C_{tot} of 4.04%, while the deeper soil layer (20-40cm) had an average C_{tot} of 2.56%. The soil in transect B showed slightly higher carbon concentrations, with 5.15% C_{tot} in the upper soil layer and 3.14% C_{tot} in the deeper soil layer. When averaging over soil depth, Transect B showed higher carbon contents, with an overall average C_{tot} of 4.14% compared to the average C_{tot} of transect A being 3.6%. In terms of nitrogen, transect B revealed higher values for both total nitrogen (N_{tot}) and C/N ratio. Regarding acidity, transect A had a slightly higher mean pH (6.12) than transect B (5.94), indicating marginally less acidic conditions in transect A.

Table 1: Results of soil analysis.

Sample	Clay (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Texture	Ctot (%)	Ntot (%)	C/N	pH
A2 (0-20cm)	41.52	14.73	43.75	loamy clay	3.02	0.25	12.01	6.03
A2 (20-50cm)					2.77	0.22	12.47	6.27
A6 (0-20cm)	45.45	4.05	50.50	loamy clay	3.55	0.30	11.86	5.94
A6 (20-50cm)					2.22	0.18	12.20	6.11
A8 (0-20cm)	40.56	20.60	38.84	loamy clay	5.55	0.39	14.16	6.18
A8 (20-50cm)					2.70	0.21	12.67	6.18
B1 (0-20cm)	40.46	26.37	33.17	loamy clay	4.13	0.31	13.26	5.71
B1 (20-50cm)					3.51	0.25	13.98	6.16
B4 (0-20cm)	47.03	9.24	43.73	loamy clay	6.20	0.54	11.52	5.80
B4 (20-50cm)					2.76	0.22	12.35	6.10

The soil moisture (θ) and soil temperature values measured by the TOMST TMS-4 revealed distinct temporal and spatial patterns, which will be analysed in the following sections 4.2.2 and **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** When averaging soil parameters over the entire measurement period and all measurement points, transect B proved to be a significantly wetter location ($\theta = 62.3\%$) compared to transect A ($\theta=22.1\%$). The difference in mean soil temperature between the two transects is less pronounced, with transect B showing a slightly higher mean soil temperature (A: 23.1°C, B: 23.8°C). This difference could erase due to the measurement procedure starting with transect A at earlier daytimes.

Kommentiert [MV9]: Macht es sinn hier auch die Daten des Piezometers oder der anderen Messstelle (mit denen die data gaps gefüllt wurden) anzuführen?

Kommentiert [DB10R9]: Ich denke nicht, da wir mit dem Piezometer nur Grundwasser an Transekt A gemessen haben. Daher fehlt die Möglichkeit zum Vergleich zwischen den Sites, um den es in diesem Kapitel geht.

4.2 Comparison of CO₂ flux dynamics between transects A & B

4.2.1 Descriptive statistics of CO₂ flux

The characteristics of the measured CO₂ fluxes for each transect can be examined from three perspectives: a mean perspective over time and space, a temporal perspective over the study period (Figure 7, **Figure 9**), and a spatial perspective across transect measuring points (Figure 8, Figure 10). Overall, both transect A and B revealed only positive flux values, indicating CO₂ emission (excluding photosynthesis) at all sites and measurement days. In the following, descriptive values of fluxes are presented as mean flux ± standard deviation. The mean CO₂ flux was higher in transect A than in transect B (A: $3,37 \pm 1,47 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: $3,11 \pm 2,30 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Standard deviation and therefore variation was higher among flux values of transect B (A: ± 1,47; B ± 2,30). The observation of higher flux variation in transect B is underlined by the broader range of flux values in transect B (A: min. 0,41 to max. 7,98 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: min. 0,67 to max. 12,73 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Looking at the temporal distribution of the measurements, a trend towards larger mean CO₂ fluxes on later measurement days can be observed. This circumstance is particularly pronounced for flux values of transect A (Figure 7). The standard deviation of CO₂ fluxes in both transects A and B increases similarly at later measurement dates (Figure 7, **Figure 9**). Regarding the spatial variability of CO₂ fluxes, topographic impacts in both transects can be discerned. CO₂ fluxes in transect A were lower at measuring points lying within the former oxbow (A4, A5, A6 in Figure 8) than at higher locations (A1, A2, A3, A7, A8 in Figure 8), with the exception of point A9 seemingly influenced by a different hydrogeological system. Fluxes in transect B decreased with terrain elevation towards the marshy depression (B4, B5 in Figure 10). The relationships between fluxes, topography and local environmental conditions are further examined in sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3. Comparing the variation of CO₂ fluxes between the temporal and the spatial perspective, values of spatial standard deviation (sd) exceeded values of temporal standard deviation for both transect A (temporal mean sd: $0,89 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; spatial mean sd: $1,34 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and transect B (temporal mean sd: $1,54 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; spatial mean sd: $2,00 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). This is indicating higher variability of CO₂ flux across space than over the study period.

Figure 7: Transect A, CO₂ flux per day of measurement

Figure 8: Transect A, CO₂ flux per measuring point.

Figure 9: Transect B, CO₂ flux per day of measurement.

Figure 10: Transect B, CO₂ flux per measuring point.

To separate soil and plant respiration, the vegetation cover at measuring point B2NPC was removed. The measurement results were highly variable but revealed a large impact of plant respiration on the 17.06.2026 (**Figure 11**). Averages over the three measurement days showed a

lower CO₂ flux at measurement point B2NPC, indicating that plant respiration contributes a significant part to R_{eco} (B2NPC: 4,41 ± 1,88 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹; B2: 5,65 ± 3,59 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹).

Figure 11: Effect of plant cover removal on CO₂ flux.

4.2.2 Environmental parameters: Characteristics and interdependencies

Graphing soil temperature, soil moisture, and CO₂ flux measurements on a single measurement basis facilitates the examination of individual flux events and influential environmental parameters (**Figure 12, Figure 13**). In transect A, particularly large CO₂ fluxes, like on the 17.06.25 at measuring points A1 (7,18 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹) or on the 23.06.25 at measuring point A8 (7,98 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹) can be associated with simultaneous high soil temperature (A1: 27,3 C°, A8: 33,6 C°) and low soil moisture conditions (A1: 18,4%, A8: 0,01%). The same applies to transect B's outliers at measuring point B1 on the 17.06.25 (12,73 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹) and point B2 on the 17.06.25 (9.71 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹), which appear simultaneously with high soil temperature (B1: 23,4 °C, B2: 27,8°C) and relatively low soil moisture (B1: 20,5%, B2: 34,0%). To identify trends in environmental parameters and related CO₂ flux, mean values over study period (**Figure 1414, Figure 155**) and across transect (**Figure 16, Figure 17**) reduce information to a more concise level. In terms of temporal trends, mean soil temperature rises, while mean soil moisture and groundwater level decrease over progressing study period. Simultaneously with the seasonal changes in environmental parameters, mean CO₂ emissions increase in both transects (**Figure 1414,**

Figure 155). High mean soil temperature and low mean soil moisture measurements mostly accompany high mean CO₂ fluxes and low mean soil temperature and high mean soil moisture measurements mostly accompany low mean CO₂ fluxes.

Figure 12: Transect A, CO₂ flux and environmental parameters.

Figure 13: Transect B, CO₂ flux and environmental parameters.

Figure 14: Transect A, mean CO₂ flux and mean environmental parameters over time.

Figure 15: Transect B, mean CO₂ flux and mean environmental parameters over time.

Figure 16: Transect A, mean CO₂ flux and mean environmental parameters across transect.

Figure 17: Transect B, mean CO₂ flux and mean environmental parameters over transect.

Looking at the spatial variability, differences in mean soil temperature in both transects are negligible and can be explained by the measurement procedure starting at transect points A1 and B1 earlier in the day and measuring in ascending order throughout the day. Across transect A, the influence of the former oxbow on mean soil moisture conditions can be discerned (Figure 16). Measurement points within the former oxbow (A4-A6) showed high mean soil moisture levels, associated with significantly lower mean CO₂ fluxes. Measuring point A9 is affected by a different hydrogeology but confirms the observation of low mean CO₂ flux and synchronous high mean soil moisture. Across transect B, mean soil moisture values increased towards the marshy depression around measuring points B4 and B5, accompanied by decreasing mean CO₂ fluxes (Figure 17).

4.2.3 GAM analysis of CO₂ flux and environmental parameters

The effects of soil temperature and soil moisture on CO₂ flux found in the temporal and spatial representations above, can be further elaborated by the GAM results. The visualization of predictor effects on CO₂ flux gives a good first impression of variable proportionalities. The single smooth effect plots show the values of deviation from the average CO₂ flux (continuous line) together with a 95% confidence interval (dashed lines). Transect A's single plots show a positive effect of soil temperature on CO₂ flux (Figure 18, left). The effect of soil temperature is first smaller than the intercept, indicated by negative values, but then exceeds the intercept at around 25°C. This trend is consistent with the previous finding of increasing CO₂ fluxes corresponding to rising soil temperatures. Soil moisture exhibits a strongly non-linear, slightly negative relationship with CO₂ flux, also matching previous findings of seasonal soil moisture decrease and CO₂ flux increase (Figure 18, right). Combining the two predictor's effects into a 2D contour plot reveals hotspot areas of CO₂ flux (Figure 19). Peak CO₂ flux occurs over the total soil moisture range, when soil temperature exceeds values over 25°C. A second smaller CO₂ flux hotspot occurs at lower soil temperatures (10-20°C) in combination with low soil moisture (10-20%).

Figure 18: GAM predictor effects for CO₂ flux in transect A.

Figure 19: CO₂ flux contour plot for transect A.

Transect B's GAM revealed that the effect of the predictor soil temperature on CO₂ flux is statistically insignificant (Table 4). Therefore, only the 1D-effect of soil moisture is plotted (Figure 20). At low soil moisture values, the smooth term effect is large and reveals a negative trend with growing soil moisture. This fits to the previously observed spatial pattern in transect B. Greater CO₂ fluxes appear at drier measuring points (B1-B3) and smaller CO₂ fluxes occur at measuring points that are strongly influenced by soil water (B4, B5). Due to the high significance of transect B's GAM interaction term (Table 4), transect B's contour plot is considered despite insignificance of predictor soil

temperature (**Figure 21**). The plot shows a clear single hotspot of CO₂ flux at low soil moisture levels (<20%) and medium soil temperature (20–25°C).

Effect of SM on CO2

Figure 20: GAM predictor effect of soil moisture (SM) on CO₂ flux in transect B.

Contour Plot CO₂: Transect B

Figure 21: CO₂ flux contour plot for transect B (ST = soil temperature, SM = soil moisture).

To account for the concurvity of the environmental parameters, GAMs provide concurvity indices. To additionally rate model predictors by their explanatory power, the unique information content contributed by each parameter and their interaction was quantified by D² partitioning (see section 0). The concurvity indices of transect A's GAM are similar and indicate medium concurvity (**Table 2**). Regarding D² partitioning, when soil temperature enters the model first, it accounts for 50,7% of D² and soil moisture is adding additional 5,4% of unique D² (**Table 2**). When soil moisture enters

first, the model's D^2 equals 41,4%, and soil temperature subsequently adds a unique D^2 of 14,7%. This high unique D^2 value for soil temperature suggests that soil temperature has a greater individual influence on CO_2 flux than soil moisture. The tensor smooth representing combined explanatory power for soil moisture and soil temperature was insignificant for transect A. The GAM analysis is corroborated by the results of mutual information analysis, revealing higher RMI between CO_2 flux and soil temperature than between CO_2 flux and soil moisture (Table 3).

Table 2: Deviance partitioning results for CO_2 flux in transect A.

GAM Transect A				
Predictor	p-value	Concurvity	First D^2	Second (Unique) D^2
ST	<0.001***	0.435	0.507	0.147
SM	0.004**	0.421	0.414	0.054
Interaction	0.860	-	-	<0.001

Significance levels: *** highly significant, ** very significant, * significant, - weakly significant

Table 3: Information theory results for CO_2 flux in transect A.

RMI: Transect A		
Predictor	RMI	Sign. ($\alpha=0.99$)
ST	0.229	YES
SM	0.201	YES

Concurvity indices of transect B's GAM (SM: 0,219, ST: 0,430) point out more redundant information within soil temperature data (Table 4). In fact, the soil temperature smooth is not statistically relevant. When soil moisture enters the model for D^2 partitioning first, it accounts for 21,1% of D^2 . The unique D^2 of soil moisture accounts for 16,6%, which is however surpassed by the interaction term adding 50,9% unique D^2 to the model. Transect B's GAM is therefore dominated by the interaction term and parameter soil moisture. RMI results were not statistically significant and are therefore excluded.

Table 4: Deviance partitioning results for CO_2 flux in transect B.

GAM Transect B				
Predictor	p-value	Concurvity	First D^2	Second (Unique) D^2
ST	0.067	0.430	0.100	0.055

SM	<0.001***	0.219	0.211	0.166
Interaction	<0.001***	-	-	0.509

Significance levels: *** highly significant, ** very significant, * significant, . weakly significant

4.2.4 Summary of CO₂ flux dynamics

Across the entire observation period, both transects exhibited exclusively positive CO₂ fluxes. Mean CO₂ flux was slightly higher in transect A than in transect B, while transect B showed greater flux variability. Generally, spatial variability exceeded temporal variability, indicating that site-specific environmental conditions outweighed seasonal changes during the observation time. Over the study period soil temperature increased while soil moisture and groundwater level declined accompanied by clearly rising CO₂ fluxes in transect A and slightly rising CO₂ fluxes in transect B. In both transects, spatial patterns were shaped by topographic and hydrogeological conditions. Lower CO₂ fluxes appeared at wetter, low-lying positions whereas higher CO₂ fluxes occurred at drier, higher positions. The GAM results underline the above-described dependencies: Predictor-effect plots for transect A show a positive temperature effect approving the observed seasonal pattern of CO₂ flux simultaneously rising with soil temperature. The effect curve of soil moisture revealed a non-linear, slightly negative effect corresponding to observed CO₂ flux reduction at moister transect segments. These findings reappear in transect A's contour plot, showing a CO₂ flux hotspot at high temperatures and decreasing CO₂ flux with rising soil moisture. Regarding transect A's D² partitioning results, soil temperature is highly significant and contributes more unique explanatory power than soil moisture. Soil moisture in transect A is also very significant although adding less unique D². These findings fit the observed medium GAM concavity indices, revealing partially doubled information in soil temperature and soil moisture trends. However, some unique information contributed by soil moisture is contained in the spatial CO₂ flux curve revealing the former oxbow's impact. Regarding transect B's predictor plots, soil moisture has a strong, negative effect, which reflects CO₂ flux decrease towards the marshy depression. Soil temperature as a single predictor is not statistically significant, but the interaction term with soil moisture is. The contour plot reveals a clear CO₂ flux hotspot at low soil moisture and medium to high soil temperature consistent with increased fluxes at drier, higher-lying points. Unique D² contributed by the interaction term and soil moisture, confirms transect B's soil moisture dependence.

Overall, descriptive patterns and GAMs converge on the following key points: Over time, CO₂ flux increases with rising temperature and declining moisture. Across space, wetter, low-lying positions show lower fluxes in both transects. Predictor dominance differs by site. Temperature dominates transect A and soil moisture dominates transect B. Moreover, secondary predictor effects diverge. Whereas in transect A soil moisture is significant and shapes the CO₂ flux curve along the former oxbow, soil temperature in transect B only matters within the interaction term.

4.3 Comparison of CH₄ flux dynamics between transects A & B

4.3.1 Descriptive statistics of CH₄ flux

The three perspectives on flux characteristics account for CH₄ as well. Examined are the mean perspective over time and space, the temporal perspective over the study period (Figure 22, Figure 24), and the spatial perspective across transect measuring points (Figure 23, Figure 25). In contrast to CO₂ fluxes, negative as well as positive CH₄ fluxes were observed, indicating both sink and source behaviour within the study area. Transect A acted solely as CH₄ sink, whereas transect B occasionally emitted CH₄. Descriptive values of CH₄ fluxes are presented as mean flux ± standard deviation. Transect A had a higher mean CH₄ uptake than transect B (A: $-0,53 \pm 0,38 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: $-0,34 \pm 0,60 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Standard deviation and therefore variation was higher among flux values of transect B (A: $\pm 0,38 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: $\pm 0,60 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), reflecting the more heterogeneous conditions in transect B. The higher variability of CH₄ fluxes in transect B is further reflected in its wider range of observed values (A: $-2,00$ to $-0,03 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B: $-1,92$ to $+1,60 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Regarding the temporal trends in CH₄ fluxes, intensified CH₄ flux (both directions) at later measurement dates can be observed in both transects (Figure 22, Figure 24). Simultaneously, the variation of CH₄ fluxes measured by standard deviation tended to increase with progressing study period (Figure 22, Figure 24). The spatial variability of CH₄ fluxes exhibits a similar topographic dependence as observed for CO₂ fluxes. In transect A, measuring points located within the former oxbow (A4, A5, A6) showed lower CH₄ uptake compared to higher-lying points (A1, A2, A7, A8) (Figure 23). Regarding CH₄ measurements, measuring point A3 can be assigned to the transect points influenced by the oxbow. A9 again represents a particular case, displaying relatively low CH₄ uptake despite not being situated within the former oxbow. In contrast to CO₂ fluxes the temporal and spatial variation of CH₄ fluxes was similar both in transect A (temporal mean sd: $0,29 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; spatial mean sd: $0,29 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and transect B (temporal mean sd: $0,46 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; spatial mean sd: $0,53 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Figure 22: Transect A, CH₄ flux per day of measurement.

Figure 23: Transect A, CH₄ flux per measuring point.

When visually assessing transect B's CH₄ fluxes, spatial contrasts are pronounced (**Figure 25**). The highest-lying measuring points (B1, B2) exhibited negative CH₄ fluxes with one exception at point B1 on the 26.05.25. Measuring point B3 showed CH₄ uptake on all dates except for the 19.05.2025. In contrast, the lowest-lying measuring points (B4, B5), which lie within the marshy depression, displayed alternating depletion and emission over the study period. Positive CH₄ fluxes at these points indicate a shift from CH₄ uptake to CH₄ production.

Figure 24: Transect B, CH₄ flux per day of measurement.

Figure 25: Transect B, CH₄ flux per measuring point.

The removal of vegetation cover at measuring point B2NPC on the CH₄ flux both increased and decreased B2NPC CH₄ uptake (Figure 26). When averaged over the three measurement days, the CH₄ depletion at the clear-cut site was weaker (B2: $-1.10 \pm 0.67 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; B2NPC: $-0.83 \pm 0.96 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), indicating that plant activity could contribute to methane uptake.

Figure 26: Effect of plant cover removal on CH₄ flux.

4.3.2 Environmental parameters: Characteristics and interdependencies

As with CO₂ fluxes, conjointly plotting soil temperature, soil moisture, and CH₄ flux measurements on a single-measurement basis facilitates the analysis of extreme flux events and interacting environmental conditions (Figure 27, Figure 28). Strongly negative CH₄ fluxes were seen in transect A, particularly on the 17.06.2025 and the 23.06.2025, when soil temperature measurements were among the highest observations and soil moisture measurements were among the lowest (Figure 27). Peak CH₄ uptakes occurred at measuring point A1 on the 17.06.2025 (-2,00 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹) and on the 19.05.2025 (-1,91 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹) as well as at point A2 on the 23.06.2025 (-1,59 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹). Whereas the peak CH₄ uptake at A1 on the 19.05.2025 seems to be exceptional and not directly related to soil temperature and soil moisture peaks, CH₄ uptake peaks at A1 on the 17.06.2025 and at A2 on the 23.06.2025 appeared simultaneously with high soil temperature (A1: 27,3°C; A2: 30,6°C) and relatively low soil moisture (A1: 18,3%; A2: 8,3%). In transect B, peaks of CH₄ uptake and CH₄ emission must be distinguished (Figure 28). Peak CH₄ uptake appeared at measuring points B1 and B2 on the 17.06.2025 (B1: -1,51 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹; B2: -1,47 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹). These two peaks were accompanied by high soil temperatures (27–33 °C) and relatively moderate soil moisture (25–40%). In contrast, the peak CH₄ emission observed at measuring point B5 on the 17.06.2025 (+1,60 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹) coincides with very high soil moisture (88,8%) and high soil temperature (28,8°C). Measurements on the 17.06.2025, although neither the hottest nor the driest day, encompass both maximum CH₄ uptake and maximum CH₄ emission.

Figure 27: Transect A, CH₄ flux and environmental parameters.

Figure 28: Transect B, CH₄ flux and environmental parameters.

As with CO₂ fluxes, mean values of CH₄ flux over time (Figure 29, Figure 30) and across space (Figure 31, Figure 32) facilitate the examination of the relationships between CH₄ flux and environmental parameters. As we saw in section 4.2.2, seasonal trends show increasing soil temperatures and decreasing groundwater table as well as decreasing soil moisture over the progressing study period (Figure 29). CH₄ uptake in transect A intensifies following the temporal trends in environmental parameters. Transect B's CH₄ flux however cannot be interlinked with temporal patterns of soil temperature and soil moisture (Figure 30). From a spatial perspective, soil moisture emerges as a key differentiating factor. In transect A, measuring points within the former oxbow (A4, A5, A6 in Figure 31) exhibited higher mean soil moisture levels and simultaneously reduced mean CH₄ uptake compared to drier locations (A1, A2, A3, A7, A8 in Figure 31). In transect B, the hydrological gradient towards the marshy depression is even more pronounced. Measuring points B4 and B5 showed very high mean soil moisture values, while CH₄ fluxes frequently shifted from negative to positive values, indicating methane emissions under waterlogged conditions (Figure 32).

Figure 29: Transect A, mean CH₄ flux and mean environmental parameters over time.

Figure 30: Transect B, mean CH₄ flux and mean environmental parameters over time.

Figure 31: Transect A, mean CH₄ flux and mean environmental parameters across space.

Figure 32: Transect B, mean CH₄ flux and mean environmental parameters across space.

4.3.3 GAM analysis of CH₄ flux and environmental parameters

The visually assessed relationships between soil temperature, soil moisture and CH₄ flux were further examined using GAMs. As with the analysis of CO₂ flux, 1-D visualisation of smooth term effects illustrates the influence of soil temperature (ST) and soil moisture (SM) on the CH₄ flux model-intercept. In transect A's GAM the smooth term for soil temperature reveals a highly non-linear relationship with CH₄ flux (**Figure 33**, left). At intermediate soil temperatures (12–18 °C), the effect is negative, indicating reduced CH₄ uptake, whereas at higher temperatures (> 20 °C) the effect becomes slightly positive and ends up becoming indifferent (> 25 °C). The smooth effect of soil moisture shows a more consistent, mostly positive trend (**Figure 33**, right). At low soil moisture values, the term is negative, reflecting the enhanced CH₄ uptake under relatively dry conditions. With increasing soil moisture, the effect shifts towards positive values, indicating reduced CH₄ uptake. This reflects the earlier observation of lower CH₄ fluxes at measuring points lying within the former oxbow.

The 2D contour plot for transect A reveals a hotspot of CH₄ uptake at low soil temperatures (0–15 °C) and low soil moisture (0–15%). Towards higher soil moisture levels, the CH₄ uptake decreases (**Figure 34**). This pattern confirms the observation of high CH₄ uptake at relatively dry measuring points, decreasing towards measuring points lying within the former oxbow.

Figure 33: GAM predictor effects for CH₄ flux in transect A.

Figure 34: CH₄ flux contour plot for transect A.

Transect B's soil moisture smooth term of shows a non-linear but mostly positive effect on CH₄ flux (**Figure 35**). At low to moderate soil moisture values (20-40%), the smooth term is negative, indicating enhanced CH₄ uptake under comparatively dry conditions. With increasing soil moisture, the effect gradually shifts towards positive values and rises steeply beyond soil moisture values over 60%. At very high soil moisture (> 80%), strong positive smooth effects reflect the transition towards CH₄ emission.

Figure 35: GAM predictor effect for CH₄ flux in transect B.

The contour plot for transect B demonstrates decreasing CH₄ uptake with increasing soil moisture and a shift towards CH₄ emissions at soil moisture levels above approximately 80% (**Figure 36**Figure 35). In contrast, a hotspot of CH₄ uptake was found at low soil moisture and high

soil temperature. Isolines of CH₄ flux reveal a relatively high impact of soil temperature at low soil moisture but a predominant role of soil moisture at soil moisture levels exceeding 60%.

Figure 36: CH₄ flux contour plot for transect B.

To evaluate not only the direction but also the magnitude of the effects of soil temperature and soil moisture on CH₄ flux, the explanatory power of the GAM predictors was further assessed. In transect A, both soil temperature and soil moisture were statistically significant predictors (**Table 5**). Concurrency indices show that soil moisture exhibits stronger overlap with soil temperature than vice versa (SM: 0,352; ST: 0,273). Deviance partitioning revealed, that when soil temperature enters the model first, it explains 31,1% of D² and soil moisture contributes an additional 6,9% unique D². When soil moisture is entered first, it explains 22,1%, and soil temperature subsequently adds 16,0% unique D². The higher unique D² of soil temperature indicates that soil temperature exerts a stronger independent influence on transect A's CH₄ flux. The interaction term was not statistically significant. RMI analysis approved the finding of stronger correlation between CO₂ flux and soil temperature than between CO₂ flux and soil moisture (**Table 6**).

Table 5: Deviance partitioning results for CH₄ flux in transect A.

GAM Transect A				
Predictor	p-value	Concurrency	First D ²	Second (Unique) D ²
ST	<0.001***	0.273	0.311	0.160
SM	<0.001***	0.352	0.221	0.069
Interaction	0.118	-	-	0.077

Table 6: Information theory results for CH₄ flux in transect A.

RMI Transect A		
Predictor	RMI	Sign. ($\alpha=0.99$)
ST	0.186	YES
SM	0.153	NO

In transect B, soil temperature was statistically insignificant, whereas soil moisture was highly significant (Table 7). Concurvity values were low overall (SM: 0,237; ST: 0,120). Deviance partitioning showed that soil moisture explains 39,9% of D² when entered first but also contributes 36,8% of unique D². The interaction term adds 15,8% unique D², indicating combined effects of soil temperature and soil moisture despite the insignificance of soil temperature as a single predictor. RMI results are aligned with GAM results, showing a stronger influence of soil moisture on transect B's CH₄ flux (Table 8).

Table 7: Deviance partitioning results for CH₄ flux in transect B.

GAM Transect B				
Predictor	p-value	Concurvity	First D ²	Second (Unique) D ²
ST	0.438	0.120	0.070	0.039
SM	<0.001***	0.237	0.399	0.368
Interaction	0.001**	-	-	0.158

Table 8: Information theory results for CH₄ flux in transect B.

RMI Transect A		
Predictor	RMI	Sign. ($\alpha=0.99$)
ST	0.337	NO
SM	0.417	YES

4.3.4 Summary of CH₄ flux dynamics

Across the observation period, both sink and source CH₄ fluxes occurred, with transect A showing stronger mean CH₄ uptake than transect B. As for CO₂ flux, transect B exhibited higher variability. In contrast to CO₂, temporal and spatial variability of CH₄ were of similar magnitude in both transects, indicating evenly distributed variation across time and space. Over time, CH₄ flux intensified (both directions) later in the season in both transects. Again, only transect A's

temporal CH₄ flux pattern aligned clearly with seasonal trends in environmental parameters. Transect B's CH₄ flux was strongly affected by spatial trends. Across space, soil moisture was the key differentiator again. In transect A, moister, low-lying points within the former oxbow revealed reduced CH₄ uptake compared to drier, higher segments. In transect B the marshy depression reached very high moisture and frequently shifted from CH₄ uptake to emission. GAM results corroborate these patterns and prove predictor dominance. As with transect A's CO₂ flux, both soil temperature and soil moisture in transect A's GAM were significant, with soil temperature contributing more unique explanatory power than soil moisture. Predictor-effect plots for transect A's CH₄ flux show a non-linear temperature effect and a moisture effect that shifts from a negative effect (higher CH₄ uptake) at low moisture to a positive effect (lower CH₄ uptake) with increasing moisture. These soil moisture effects reflect the CH₄ flux curve in transect A's oxbow area. The contour plot reveals a CH₄ uptake hotspot at lower soil temperature and low soil moisture, diminishing with higher moisture. In transect B, soil temperature as a single predictor was insignificant, while soil moisture was highly significant and, together with the interaction term, dominated model explanatory power. Transect B's soil moisture effect transitions from very negative values at lower soil moisture to rapidly increasing positive values. This corroborates the high CH₄ uptake found at higher, dryer locations and the decrease in CH₄ uptake and periodic shift to emission under very moist conditions. The contour plot aligns with previous findings showing two hotspots: One for CH₄ uptake associated with low moisture and high temperature representing transect B's high-lying measuring points and one for CH₄ emission at very high soil moisture representing measurements at the marshy depression.

Overall, descriptive patterns and GAMs of CH₄ flux converge on the following key points: Over the study period both negative and positive CH₄ fluxes intensified. Across space, wetter, low-lying positions showed reduced uptake or even emission, that occurred in transect B's marshy depression. As with CO₂, environmental parameter dominance differs by site: Soil temperature dominates transect A followed by significant soil moisture. Transect B is mainly affected by soil moisture and the interaction term, whereas soil temperature solely is insignificant.

5 Discussion

The following discussion puts the measured CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes and relevant environmental parameters into the context of existing literature. Furthermore, implications for land management of the Auenreservat Marchegg are drawn.

5.1 CO₂ and CH₄ flux magnitudes in similar literature

5.1.1 CO₂ flux magnitudes

Similar studies conducted in temperate upland and riparian forest areas (Darenova et al. 2016; Jacinthe 2015; Walkiewicz et al. 2025) or specifically in floodplain areas at Morava and Danube River (Acosta et al. 2017; Schindlbacher et al. 2022) found CO₂ fluxes of the same magnitude and flux direction. Since these studies also used opaque chambers to measure fluxes, their positive CO₂ flux values (R_{eco}) are directly comparable to those obtained in this study. At an alluvial floodplain along the Morava River in the southern Czech Republic, north of Marchegg, CO₂ fluxes ranged from 1,59 to 8,54 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹ during the 2016 growing season (Acosta et al. 2017). These findings match this study's CO₂ flux range, which varied between 0,41 - 12,73 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹ across both transects. The mean CO₂ flux found 15km away from Marchegg at an infrequently flooded forest site in the Danube National Park, was 2,48 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹ corresponding to the magnitude of transect A's mean flux being 3,37 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹ and transect B's mean flux being 3,11 μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹. However, the results cannot be compared directly, since the CO₂ flux measured at Danube National Park is an annual mean value in contrast to this study's measurements covering only the spring months April to June.

5.1.2 CH₄ flux magnitudes

CH₄ fluxes measured alongside CO₂ fluxes in a temperate forest in Poland (Walkiewicz et al. 2025), a riparian grassland in China (Gong et al. 2024), a riparian forest/grassland in Indiana, U.S. (Jacinthe 2015), and in the Danube National Park (Schindlbacher et al. 2022) match CH₄ flux magnitudes observed in Auenreservat Marchegg. Jacinthe found a mean annual CH₄ flux of -0,37 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹ at a riparian grassland site along White River in Indiana, which is comparable to the magnitude of mean CH₄ fluxes of transect A (-0.53 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹) and transect B (-0.34 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹). Measurements near Stopfenreuth in the Danube National Park were the geographically closest CH₄ references found within this research with a mean annual flux of -0,67 nmol CH₄ m⁻² s⁻¹ at an infrequently flooded forest site (Schindlbacher et al. 2022). However, direct numerical comparability with this study's CH₄ fluxes is again limited due to different measurement periods. CH₄ fluxes reported in comparable studies not only match the observed flux magnitude but also exhibit similar flux characteristics. These sites mostly acted as CH₄ sinks, with occasional short-term shifts to CH₄ emission (Jacinthe 2015; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Walkiewicz et al. 2025). Positive fluxes (emissions) consistently occurred during periods of high soil water content, i.e. spring thaw period (Schindlbacher et al. 2022) and rewetting events like heavy rainfall (Gong et al. 2024; Schindlbacher et al. 2022) or floods (Jacinthe 2015; Schindlbacher et al. 2022). This general CH₄ sink behaviour was also found in transect A and B, with some measuring points of transect B shifting to CH₄ emission under high soil water influence.

Kommentiert [AL11]: Interteilen in CO₂ und CH₄, und dann noch etwas genauer auch die einzelnen Einflussfaktoren?

5.2 Environmental controls on CO₂ and CH₄ flux in the literature

5.2.1 Controls of CO₂ fluxes

Controlling environmental factors of CO₂ (and CH₄) fluxes mentioned in comparable literature encompassed soil and vegetation parameters. Among soil parameters there is broad consensus on CO₂ flux revealing the strongest interaction with soil temperature, (Acosta et al. 2017; Jacinthe 2015; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Walkiewicz et al. 2025), followed by soil water content (Acosta et al. 2017; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Walkiewicz et al. 2025). The studies of CO₂ fluxes along Morava and Danube river found a strong positive correlation with soil temperature and weak negative correlation with soil moisture (Acosta et al. 2017; Schindlbacher et al. 2022). CO₂ flux dynamics examined in the Czech Republic across different ecosystems, like spruce and beech forests, a grassland and a wetland, showed decreasing CO₂ fluxes with increasing soil moisture across all ecosystem types (Darenova et al. 2016). These observations are consistent with this study's finding of a strong positive soil temperature and a weak negative soil moisture impact on CO₂ flux found in transect A. Transect B, exhibiting wetter and more spatially variable conditions, revealed a significant negative relationship between CO₂ flux and soil moisture and a negligible impact of soil temperature. Similar flux conditions were found at 6 floodplain sites along Difficult Run, Maryland U.S. (Batson et al. 2015). 5 of the 6 sites are situated in fluvial landforms and are therefore strongly influenced by surface and subsurface water flow. This suggests that soil moisture might only become a dominant parameter when a certain moisture threshold is exceeded, which occurs under highly hydric conditions such as those observed in transect B and along Difficult Run River.

Other influential environmental parameters on CO₂ flux found in the literature are soil carbon content (Acosta et al. 2017; Batson et al. 2015; Gong et al. 2024; Schindlbacher et al. 2022), soil pH (Acosta et al. 2017; Gong et al. 2024) or vegetation indices like below and above ground biomass (Darenova et al. 2016; Gong et al. 2024), grass height in floodplain grasslands (Darenova et al. 2016), or forest type (Walkiewicz et al. 2025).

5.2.2 Controls of CH₄ fluxes

Regarding environmental drivers of CH₄ fluxes, there is strong consensus on soil moisture exerting the primary control, revealing a strong positive correlation with CH₄ flux across diverse climatic and ecological conditions (Batson et al. 2015; Jacinthe 2015; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Walkiewicz et al. 2025). Several studies found evidence of peak CH₄ emission triggered by sudden soil moisture increases during precipitation or flood events (Batson et al. 2015; Gong et al. 2024; Schindlbacher et al. 2022; Walkiewicz et al. 2025). However, the extent to which precipitation or flooding can affect CH₄ fluxes depends on local soil and vegetation conditions, which either promote waterlogging or facilitate fast drainage (Schindlbacher et al. 2022). The role of soil temperature on CH₄ flux is more contested, since warm soil conditions can favour microbially-mediated processes leading to both CH₄ consumption and production (Jacinthe 2015). Walkiewicz et al. found positive correlation between soil temperature and CH₄ consumption in combination with dry soil conditions in deciduous temperate forests (Walkiewicz et al. 2025). The high CH₄ uptake rates observed on hot and dry days in transect A align with this finding. The dominance of soil temperature on transect A's CH₄ fluxes likely reflects its sun- and wind-exposed position, which promotes warmer and drier surface conditions where methanotrophic activity follows thermal seasonality. Nevertheless, soil moisture significantly influenced transect A's CH₄ fluxes across the former oxbow, consistent with the previously described positive correlation between rising soil moisture and decreasing CH₄ uptake. Transect B approved the prevailing paradigm of soil moisture dominating CH₄ flux. Similar to findings of Schindlbacher et

al. and Jacinthe, no relevant individual impact of soil temperature was found in transect B. However, transect B's GAM revealed a strong interactive effect of soil temperature and soil moisture, that could stem from soil temperature modulating anaerobic microbial activity under waterlogged conditions, a mechanism also discussed in the context of Dutch peatlands (Buzacott et al. 2024). The differing influence of soil temperature on CH₄ flux between transects A and B may be caused by contrasting site-specific conditions. In transect B, the soil is covered by tall grass and further shaded by the nearby forest, reducing direct solar heating. Additionally, periodic surface water stagnation and high soil moisture increase the soil's heat capacity, buffering temperature fluctuations. Together, these factors may explain why soil temperature does not significantly affect CH₄ flux in transect B. Beyond soil moisture and soil temperature, other influential environmental parameters on CH₄ flux found in literature are soil texture indices like clay and silt content (Batson et al. 2015; Jacinthe 2015; Walkiewicz et al. 2025), soil pH (Gong et al. 2024), ammonium concentration (Batson et al. 2015; Gong et al. 2024; Walkiewicz et al. 2025) and soil carbon content (Walkiewicz et al. 2025).

5.3 Implications for land management in the Auenreservat as NCS

Land management practices when implemented as NCS intend to either reduce GHG emissions at source or to foster carbon sequestration (Griscom et al. 2017). To assess the impact of land management on GHG emissions, different gases can be merged into one comprehensive unit, called the Global Warming Potential (GWP) (Gong et al. 2024). By definition of the IPCC, the GWP quantifies the cumulative radiative forcing of a pulse emission of a greenhouse gas relative to CO₂ over a specified time horizon, usually 20 or 100 years (IPCC 2021). The GWP itself is dimensionless but indicates the relation between the radiative forcing effect of 1 kg of a GHG compared to 1 kg CO₂. Therefore, integrated GHG emissions are usually expressed in kg CO₂ equivalent (CO₂-eq). The current GWP of CH₄ (excluding climate feedbacks) for a 100-year time span equals 27,2 (IPCC 2021). Based on this, measured CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes from transects A and B can be expressed in CO₂ equivalents by multiplying CH₄ fluxes by 27,2, converting the flux unit and adding them to the CO₂ fluxes. Since both transects acted as mean CH₄ sinks, the overall GHG fluxes are smaller than CO₂ fluxes. Transect A, representing grazing land management, showed a GWP of 3,35 μmol CO₂-eq m⁻² s⁻¹, compared to the mowed transect B which revealed a GWP of 3,10 μmol CO₂-eq m⁻² s⁻¹. Based on these results, the mowing regime of transect B appears to have resulted in a lower carbon gas emission over the study period. However, the CO₂ fluxes in this study were measured using an opaque chamber, which inhibits photosynthesis. As a result, the observed flux corresponds to R_{eco} without considering CO₂ uptake by primary production. Yet, CO₂ assimilation is a critical component for accurately evaluating the net climate impact (NEE) of an ecosystem and its land management regime (Lankreijer et al. 2009; Reichstein et al. 2005; Zhao et al. 2019). Studies on CO₂ fluxes of Swedish and Finnish forest soils found estival photosynthesis exceeding soil and plant cover respiration rates (Lankreijer et al. 2009). Furthermore, carbon fluxes were measured only during the period from April to June, whereas year-round measurements are necessary to draw robust conclusions about the effects of land management practices. To complete the GWP assessment, N₂O fluxes should also be taken into account (Gong et al. 2024). Regarding carbon sequestration, the observed soil carbon contents indicate slightly higher carbon sequestration in transect B. To completely assess the carbon sequestration effect of a land management type, key components of the carbon cycle, such as soil and vegetation carbon stocks, as well as lateral carbon inputs and outputs (Were et al., 2019) should be quantified.

Considering both GHG emission and soil carbon content, and accounting for the aforementioned limitations, the findings suggest that mowing represents a more effective land management strategy for climate change mitigation. However, present observations indicate that site-specific

environmental conditions and fine scale microtopographic variation might have a stronger effect on the net climate impact than present land management practices. This inference was drawn based on the observation, that differences in mean fluxes between measuring points within transects A and B exceeded differences in mean fluxes between transect A and B. Land management practices however impact site-specific conditions, for example by fostering plant cover or by improving soil water drainage to avoid CH₄ emissions from waterlogged soils. Vegetation cover, such as the tall grass maintained by land management practice of transect B can buffer soil temperature fluctuations, thereby reducing thermally driven CO₂ production. In future studies, the use of transparent measurement chambers would enable the quantification of photosynthesis and thereby net ecosystem exchange (NEE), allowing for a more comprehensive assessment of the net carbon balance of ecosystems and their land management. Year-round or multi-year measurements are necessary to account for interannual variability and to reliably characterize the long-term sink or source behavior of a site (Baldocchi et al. 2018). Summer drought stress and autumn flooding events, both relevant periods in floodplain systems (Gong et al. 2024; Schindlbacher et al. 2022), were also not captured within this study. To minimize the influence of site-specific factors greater spatial resolution of GHG fluxes and environmental parameters is required. Moreover, the evaluation of land management effects would be more robust if multiple transects per management type were observed. The use of a single transect makes it impossible to differentiate, if observed variations in GHG fluxes stem from management practices or from site-specific conditions.

6 Conclusion

This study investigated greenhouse gas flux dynamics in a restored floodplain grassland within the Auenreservat Marchegg as part of the EU REWET project. Measurements of CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes, together with soil temperature, soil moisture and groundwater level, were conducted along two transects representing contrasting land management types (i.e. grazing in transect A and mowing in transect B). Measurements were taken in the period from April to June 2025 and were postprocessed to obtain flux descriptive statistics and to detect spatial and temporal variability patterns. By utilizing General Additive Models and Information-Theoretic approaches, the study aimed to identify and disentangle influential environmental parameters.

Both transects consistently acted as sources of CO₂, with mean fluxes of $3,37 \pm 1,47 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in transect A and $3,11 \pm 2,30 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in transect B. In contrast, CH₄ fluxes indicated a general sink behaviour, with mean fluxes of $-0,53 \pm 0,38 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in transect A and $-0,34 \pm 0,60 \text{ nmol CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in transect B, while occasional emissions occurred under high soil moisture conditions. Regarding temporal variability patterns, CO₂ fluxes increased over time in both transects, reflecting rising soil temperatures and declining soil moisture during the study period. Spatially, CO₂ fluxes were consistently lower in wetter, low-lying positions (former oxbow in transect A and marshy depression in transect B) and higher at drier, elevated locations. Notably, spatial variability exceeded temporal variability in both transects, highlighting the importance of small-scale environmental heterogeneity. In contrast, CH₄ fluxes showed similar magnitudes of spatial and temporal variability, with uptake intensifying over time in transect A, while transect B exhibited strong spatial contrasts, including shifts from uptake to emission in waterlogged zones. The separation of soil and plant respiration at measurement points B2 and B2NPC revealed that vegetation contributes substantially to ecosystem respiration. Mean CO₂ fluxes were lower after vegetation removal ($4.41 \pm 1.88 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) compared to intact conditions ($5.65 \pm 3.59 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Regarding environmental controls, strong differences emerged between the transects. In transect A, soil temperature was the most relevant parameter for both CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes, with soil moisture exerting a secondary but still significant influence. In contrast, transect B was primarily controlled by soil moisture and its interaction with soil temperature, while soil temperature alone was insignificant. These findings reflect the stronger hydrological heterogeneity and higher mean soil moisture in transect B, where water availability influences both aerobic respiration and anaerobic methane production processes.

From a climate change mitigation perspective, transect B revealed the lower overall GWP. The grazed transect A exhibited slightly higher CO₂ emissions but stronger CH₄ uptake, whereas the mown transect B showed lower mean CO₂ fluxes but higher variability and episodic CH₄ emissions under wet conditions. Nevertheless, neither management type can be clearly identified as superior based on the present dataset. CO₂ measurements were conducted using an opaque chamber, that excludes photosynthetic uptake and therefore cannot be used to assess the net greenhouse gas balance. Furthermore, the study period shows only a section of the flux dynamics over the course of the year. Finally, present observations suggest that hydrological conditions and microtopography may outweigh the current land management effects in determining the net climate impact. Nevertheless, land management actions targeting site-specific conditions, such as improving soil drainage while preserving carbon sequestration capacity or reducing direct solar exposure, may serve as valuable mitigation strategies.

Future research should focus on including CO₂ uptake by photosynthesis, extending measurement periods across full annual cycles and integrating additional carbon pool assessments. In particular, coupling complete flux measurements with long-term observations of hydrological and vegetation dynamics would improve the robustness of management

recommendations and enable a more comprehensive evaluation of floodplain ecosystems as nature-based climate solutions.

7 References

- Acosta, Manuel; Darenova, Eva; Dušek, Jiří; Pavelka, Marian (2017): Soil carbon dioxide fluxes in a mixed floodplain forest in the Czech Republic. In: *European Journal of Soil Biology* 82, S. 35–42. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejsobi.2017.08.006.
- Altor, Anne E.; Mitsch, William J. (2008): Methane and carbon dioxide dynamics in wetland mesocosms: effects of hydrology and soils. In: *Ecological Applications* 18 (5), S. 1307–1320. DOI: 10.1890/07-0009.1.
- Angle, Jordan C.; Morin, Timothy H.; Solden, Lindsey M.; Narrowe, Adrienne B.; Smith, Garrett J.; Borton, Mikayla A. et al. (2017): Methanogenesis in oxygenated soils is a substantial fraction of wetland methane emissions. In: *Nat Commun* 8 (1), S. 1567. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-017-01753-4.
- Asmuth, Jos R. von; Maas, Kees; Bakker, Mark; Petersen, Jörg (2008): Modeling time series of ground water head fluctuations subjected to multiple stresses. In: *Ground water* 46 (1), S. 30–40. DOI: 10.1111/j.1745-6584.2007.00382.x.
- Baldocchi, Dennis; Chu, Housen; Reichstein, Markus (2018): Inter-annual variability of net and gross ecosystem carbon fluxes: A review. In: *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 249, S. 520–533. DOI: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2017.05.015.
- Batson, Jackie; Noe, Gregory B.; Hupp, Cliff R.; Krauss, Ken W.; Rybicki, Nancy B.; Schenk, Edward R. (2015): Soil greenhouse gas emissions and carbon budgeting in a short-hydroperiod floodplain wetland. In: *JGR Biogeosciences* 120 (1), S. 77–95. DOI: 10.1002/2014JG002817.
- Bergamaschi, Brian A.; Bernknopf, Richard; Clow, David; Dye, Dennis; Faulkner, Stephen; Forney, William et al. (2010): A method for assessing carbon stocks, carbon sequestration: US Geological Survey (Scientific Investigations Report), 2010.
- Buzacott, Alexander J. V.; Kruijt, Bart; Bataille, Laurent; van Giersbergen, Quint; Heuts, Tom S.; Fritz, Christian et al. (2024): Drivers and Annual Totals of Methane Emissions From Dutch Peatlands. In: *Global change biology* 30 (12), e17590. DOI: 10.1111/gcb.17590.
- Conrad, Ralf (2009): The global methane cycle: recent advances in understanding the microbial processes involved. In: *Environmental microbiology reports* 1 (5), S. 285–292. DOI: 10.1111/j.1758-2229.2009.00038.x.
- Darenova, Eva; Pavelka, Marian; Macalkova, Lenka (2016): Spatial heterogeneity of CO₂ efflux and optimization of the number of measurement positions. In: *European Journal of Soil Biology* 75, S. 123–134. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejsobi.2016.05.004.
- Dybala, Kristen E.; Matzek, Virginia; Gardali, Thomas; Seavy, Nathaniel E. (2019): Carbon sequestration in riparian forests: A global synthesis and meta-analysis. In: *Global change biology* 25 (1), S. 57–67. DOI: 10.1111/gcb.14475.
- Ellis, Peter Woods; Page, Aaron Marr; Wood, Stephen; Fargione, Joseph; Masuda, Yuta J.; Carrasco Denney, Vanessa et al. (2024): The principles of natural climate solutions. In: *Nat Commun* 15 (1), S. 547. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-023-44425-2.
- Gebremichael, Amanuel W.; Osborne, Bruce; Orr, Patrick (2017): Flooding-related increases in CO₂ and N₂O emissions from a temperate coastal grassland ecosystem. In: *Biogeosciences* 14 (10), S. 2611–2626. DOI: 10.5194/bg-14-2611-2017.

Gong, Yu; Li, Xiaoling; Yi, Wenxiong; Delgado-Baquerizo, Manuel; Zhou, Guiyao; Li, Siyue et al. (2024): Extreme rainfall events eliminate the response of greenhouse gas fluxes to hydrological alterations and fertilization in a riparian ecosystem. In: *Journal of Environmental Management* 370, S. 122945. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.122945.

Griscom, Bronson W.; Adams, Justin; Ellis, Peter W.; Houghton, Richard A.; Lomax, Guy; Miteva, Daniela A. et al. (2017): Natural climate solutions. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences - PNAS* 114 (44), S. 11645–11650. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1710465114.

Hansen, James; Sato, Makiko; Kharecha, Pushker; Schuckmann, Karina von; Beerling, David J.; Cao, Junji et al. (2017): Young people's burden: requirement of negative CO₂ emissions. In: *Earth Syst. Dynam.* 8 (3), S. 577–616. DOI: 10.5194/esd-8-577-2017.

Hao, Yuefeng; Mao, Jiafu; Bachmann, Charles M.; Hoffman, Forrest M.; Koren, Gerbrand; Chen, Haishan et al. (2025): Soil moisture controls over carbon sequestration and greenhouse gas emissions: a review. In: *npj Clim Atmos Sci* 8 (1). DOI: 10.1038/s41612-024-00888-8.

Hastie, Trevor; Tibshirani, Robert (1986): Generalized Additive Models. In: *Statistical Science* 1 (3). Online verfügbar unter <https://pdodds.w3.uvm.edu/files/papers/others/1986/hastie1986a.pdf>.

Huang, Wenjuan; Hall, Steven J. (2017): Elevated moisture stimulates carbon loss from mineral soils by releasing protected organic matter. In: *Nat Commun* 8 (1), S. 1774. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-017-01998-z.

Hyndman, Rob; Athanasopoulos, George; Bergmeir, Christoph; Caceres, Gabriel; Chhay, Leanne; Kuroptev, Kirill et al. (2009): forecast: Forecasting Functions for Time Series and Linear Models.

IPCC (2021): Climate change 2021. The physical science basis : Working Group I contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.

IPCC (2023): Summary for Policymakers. In: *Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.* Unter Mitarbeit von Core Writing Team, H. Lee and J. Romero (eds.). Geneva, Switzerland.

Jacinthe, P. A. (2015): Carbon dioxide and methane fluxes in variably-flooded riparian forests. In: *Geoderma* 241–242, S. 41–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2014.10.013.

Jačka, Lukáš; Kovář, Martin; Kuželková, Marta (2023): TMS Calibration Handbook. Unter Mitarbeit von Haase, Lucie (Translation). Hg. v. TOMST s.r.o. Prague.

Jensen, Sydney A.; Webb, Jackie R.; Simpson, Gavin L.; Baulch, Helen M.; Leavitt, Peter R.; Finlay, Kerri (2023): Differential Controls of Greenhouse Gas (CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) Concentrations in Natural and Constructed Agricultural Waterbodies on the Northern Great Plains. In: *JGR Biogeosciences* 128 (4), Artikel e2022JG007261. DOI: 10.1029/2022JG007261.

Knox, S. H.; Windham-Myers, L.; Anderson, F.; Sturtevant, C.; Bergamaschi, B. (2018): Direct and Indirect Effects of Tides on Ecosystem-Scale CO₂ Exchange in a Brackish Tidal Marsh in Northern California. In: *JGR Biogeosciences* 123 (3), S. 787–806. DOI: 10.1002/2017JG004048.

Lai, Jiangshan; Tang, Jing; Li, Tingyuan; Zhang, Aiyang; Mao, Lingfeng (2024): Evaluating the relative importance of predictors in Generalized Additive Models using the gam.hp R package. In: *Plant Diversity* 46 (4), S. 542–546. DOI: 10.1016/j.pld.2024.06.002.

- Lankreijer, H. J. M.; Lindroth, A.; Strömgren, M.; Kulmala, L.; Pumpanen, J. (2009): Forest floor CO₂ flux measurements with a dark-light chamber.
- Lindenberger, A.; Rauch, H. P.; Kasak, K.; Stelzhammer, M.; Thannen, M. von der (2025): Impact of various flood conditions on the CO₂ ecosystem exchange as a component of floodplain grassland restoration. In: *Ecological Engineering* 212, S. 107489. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecoleng.2024.107489.
- Lobus, Nikolay V.; Knyazeva, Maria A.; Popova, Anna F.; Kulikovskiy, Maxim S. (2023): Carbon Footprint Reduction and Climate Change Mitigation: A Review of the Approaches, Technologies, and Implementation Challenges. In: *C* 9 (4), S. 120. DOI: 10.3390/c9040120.
- Meyer, P. E. (2022): infotheo: Information-Theoretic Measures (Version 1.2.0.1). Hg. v. CRAN. Online verfügbar unter <http://homepage.meyerp.com/software>.
- Mitsch, William J.; Bernal, Blanca; Nahlik, Amanda M.; Mander, Ülo; Zhang, Li; Anderson, Christopher J. et al. (2013): Wetlands, carbon, and climate change. In: *Landscape Ecol* 28 (4), S. 583–597. DOI: 10.1007/s10980-012-9758-8.
- Nadolski, Laura; El-Madany, Tarek S.; Nelson, Jacob; Carrara, Arnaud; Moreno, Gerardo; Nair, Richard et al. (2025): Altered seasonal sensitivity of net ecosystem exchange to controls driven by nutrient balances in a semi-arid savanna. In: *Biogeosciences* 22 (12), S. 2935–2958. DOI: 10.5194/bg-22-2935-2025.
- Nagl, Hubert (2004): Das Wasserpotential Österreichs, seine Reserven und möglichen Nutzungsmengen im Hinblick auf die Reliefabhängigkeit, die Naturraumpotential. Nutzungskonkurrenzen und die Auswirkung der Klimaänderung.
- Paustian, K.; N.H. Ravindranath; A.R. van Amstel (2006): 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. Online verfügbar unter <https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/2006-ipcc-guidelines-for-national-greenhouse-gas-inventories/>.
- Randin, Christophe F.; Jaccard, Hélène; Vittoz, Pascal; Yoccoz, Nigel G.; Guisan, Antoine (2009): Land use improves spatial predictions of mountain plant abundance but not presence-absence. In: *J Vegetation Science* 20 (6), S. 996–1008. DOI: 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2009.01098.x.
- Reichstein, Markus; Falge, Eva; Baldocchi, Dennis; Papale, Dario; Aubinet, Marc; Berbigier, Paul et al. (2005): On the separation of net ecosystem exchange into assimilation and ecosystem respiration: review and improved algorithm. In: *Global change biology* 11 (9), S. 1424–1439. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2486.2005.001002.x.
- Ruddell, Benjamin L.; Kumar, Praveen (2009): Ecohydrologic process networks: 2. Analysis and characterization. In: *Water Resources Research* 45 (3), Artikel 2008WR007280. DOI: 10.1029/2008WR007280.
- Salas, José D.; Delleur, Jacques W.; Yevjevich, Vujica M.; Lane, William L. (1980): Applied Modeling of Hydrologic Time Series. 1. Aufl.: Water Resources Publications. Online verfügbar unter <https://de.scribd.com/doc/314526193/Applied-Modeling-of-Hydrologic-Time-Series>.
- Schindlbacher, A.; Heinze, J.; Gollobich, G.; Wanek, W.; Michel, K.; Kitzler, B. (2022): Soil greenhouse gas fluxes in floodplain forests of the Danube National Park: effects of flooding and soil microclimate. In: *Biogeochemistry* 159 (2), S. 193–213. DOI: 10.1007/s10533-022-00921-z.

Schwarz, Sigrid; Aust, Günther; Englisch, Michael; Herzberger, Edwin; Kessler, David; Reiter, Rainer (2022): Bodenart und Bodenschwere - Hintergrundinformationen. In: *Mitteilungen der ÖBG* (Heft 86).

Shannon, Claude E. (1948): A Mathematical Theory of Communication. In: *The Bell System Technical Journal* (27). Online verfügbar unter <https://people.math.harvard.edu/~ctm/home/text/others/shannon/entropy/entropy.pdf>.

Sturtevant, Cove; Ruddell, Benjamin L.; Knox, Sara Helen; Verfaillie, Joseph; Matthes, Jaclyn Hatala; Oikawa, Patricia Y.; Baldocchi, Dennis (2016): Identifying scale-emergent, nonlinear, asynchronous processes of wetland methane exchange. In: *JGR Biogeosciences* 121 (1), S. 188–204. DOI: 10.1002/2015JG003054.

UNFCCC (2015): Paris Agreement. UNFCCC, FCCC/CP/2015/L.9/Rev.1. Bonn. Online verfügbar unter https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/paris_agreement.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 30.03.2026.

Walkiewicz, Anna; Bulak, Piotr; Khalil, Mohammad I.; Osborne, Bruce (2025): Assessment of soil CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes and their drivers, and their contribution to the climate change mitigation potential of forest soils in the Lublin region of Poland. In: *Eur J Forest Res* 144 (1), S. 29–52. DOI: 10.1007/s10342-024-01739-0.

Webb, Jackie R.; Leavitt, Peter R.; Simpson, Gavin L.; Baulch, Helen M.; Haig, Heather A.; Hodder, Kyle R.; Finlay, Kerri (2019): Regulation of carbon dioxide and methane in small agricultural reservoirs: optimizing potential for greenhouse gas uptake. In: *Biogeosciences* 16 (21), S. 4211–4227. DOI: 10.5194/bg-16-4211-2019.

Were, David; Kanssiime, Frank; Fetahi, Tadesse; Cooper, Ashley; Jjuuko, Charles (2019): Carbon Sequestration by Wetlands: A Critical Review of Enhancement Measures for Climate Change Mitigation. In: *Earth Syst Environ* 3 (2), S. 327–340. DOI: 10.1007/s41748-019-00094-0.

Westerhof, Jurrien; Egger, Gerhard; Schneider, Florian; Lindenberger, Anna; Zuna-Kratky, Thomas (2024): Pferdeweide Marchegg – Jahresbericht 2024. Renaturierung Untere March-Auen. Hg. v. WWF Austria (Bericht des WWF Österreich im Rahmen des LIFE+Projekts 10/NAT/AT/015). Online verfügbar unter https://www.wwf.at/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/wwf-at_Weidebericht-Auenreservat-Marchegg-2024_web.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 18.08.2025.

Wiik, E.; Haig, H. A.; Hayes, N. M.; Finlay, K.; Simpson, G. L.; Vogt, R. J.; Leavitt, P. R. (2018): Generalized Additive Models of Climatic and Metabolic Controls of Subannual Variation in pCO₂ in Productive Hardwater Lakes. In: *JGR Biogeosciences* 123 (6), S. 1940–1959. DOI: 10.1029/2018JG004506.

Wood, Simon N. (2017): *Generalized Additive Models*: Chapman and Hall/CRC.

Wood, Simon N. (2025a): *Generalized Additive Models*. In: *Annual Review of Statistics and Its Application* 12 (1), S. 497–526. DOI: 10.1146/annurev-statistics-112723-034249.

Wood, Simon N. (2025b): mgcv: Mixed GAM Computation Vehicle with Automatic Smoothness Estimation: CRAN — Comprehensive R Archive Network.

Zhao, Peng; Hammerle, Albin; Zeeman, Matthias; Wohlfahrt, Georg (2019): On the calculation of daytime CO₂ fluxes measured by automated closed transparent chambers. In: *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 263, S. 267–275. DOI: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2018.08.022.

Declaration of the use of generative AI tools

In the writing of this master's thesis, AI-based tools were used in a supportive manner. DeepL and Claude were consulted to improve the linguistic quality and clarity of the scientific English. Furthermore, ChatGPT was used to review, clean, and structure R code. Google Gemini was used as assistance for graphic design and to overlay graphics with text. All scientific content, analysis, and interpretations were developed independently by the author.

List of Figures

Figure 1: Carbon balance of the study's floodplain. Photograph by author; overlay graphics and text rendering generated with the assistance of Google Gemini (May 2026), adapted from the conceptual framework in "Fig.1 Simplified schematic overview of C cycling in wetlands" by Were et al. (2019, p. 329).	11
Figure 2: Location of the study site in Eastern Austria, Source: Location of the study site at the border of Austria and Slovakia in the nature reserve near Marchegg, Lower Austria. Lindenberger et al (2025, p.2).	15
Figure 3: Location of transect A&B within the Auenreservat Marchegg.	16
Figure 4: Vegetation changes in transect A and B over the study period.	17
Figure 5: Measurement Chamber (left) and Licor LI-7810 device (right).	19
Figure 6: TOMST TMS-4 (left) next to collar (right).	20
Figure 7: Transect A, CO ₂ flux per day of measurement	25
Figure 8: Transect A, CO ₂ flux per measuring point.	26
Figure 9: Transect B, CO ₂ flux per day of measurement.	26
Figure 10: Transect B, CO ₂ flux per measuring point.	27
Figure 11: Effect of plant cover removal on CO ₂ flux.	27
Figure 12: Transect A, CO ₂ flux and environmental parameters.	28
Figure 13: Transect B, CO ₂ flux and environmental parameters.	29
Figure 14: Transect A, mean CO ₂ flux and mean environmental parameters over time.	29
Figure 15: Transect B, mean CO ₂ flux and mean environmental parameters over time.	30
Figure 16: Transect A, mean CO ₂ flux and mean environmental parameters across transect.	30
Figure 17: Transect B, mean CO ₂ flux and mean environmental parameters over transect.	31
Figure 18: GAM predictor effects for CO ₂ flux in transect A.	32
Figure 19: CO ₂ flux contour plot for transect A.	32
Figure 20: GAM predictor effect of soil moisture (SM) on CO ₂ flux in transect B.	33
Figure 21: CO ₂ flux contour plot for transect B (ST = soil temperature, SM = soil moisture).	33
Figure 22: Transect A, CH ₄ flux per day of measurement.	36
Figure 23: Transect A, CH ₄ flux per measuring point.	37
Figure 24: Transect B, CH ₄ flux per day of measurement.	37
Figure 25: Transect B, CH ₄ flux per measuring point.	38
Figure 26: Effect of plant cover removal on CH ₄ flux.	38
Figure 27: Transect A, CH ₄ flux and environmental parameters.	39
Figure 28: Transect B, CH ₄ flux and environmental parameters.	40
Figure 29: Transect A, mean CH ₄ flux and mean environmental parameters over time.	41
Figure 30: Transect B, mean CH ₄ flux and mean environmental parameters over time.	41
Figure 31: Transect A, mean CH ₄ flux and mean environmental parameters across space.	42
Figure 32: Transect B, mean CH ₄ flux and mean environmental parameters across space.	42
Figure 33: GAM predictor effects for CH ₄ flux in transect A.	43
Figure 34: CH ₄ flux contour plot for transect A.	44
Figure 35: GAM predictor effect for CH ₄ flux in transect B.	44
Figure 36: CH ₄ flux contour plot for transect B.	45

List of Tables

Table 1: Results of soil analysis.....	24
Table 2: Deviance partitioning results for CO ₂ flux in transect A.....	34
Table 3: Information theory results for CO ₂ flux in transect A.....	34
Table 4: Deviance partitioning results for CO ₂ flux in transect B.....	34
Table 5: Deviance partitioning results for CH ₄ flux in transect A.....	45
Table 6: Information theory results for CH ₄ flux in transect A.....	46
Table 7: Deviance partitioning results for CH ₄ flux in transect B.....	46
Table 8: Information theory results for CH ₄ flux in transect B.....	46

List of Equations

Equation 1: Formula for Net Ecosystem Exchange (NEE).....	12
Equation 2: Structure of GAM for a Gaussian distribution of Y: (E(Y) = expectancy value of Y, x _i = predictor, β_0 = intercept, f _i = smooth term).....	21
Equation 3: Smooth term function in GAM (β_i = weights, b _i = basis function).....	22
Equation 4: Tensor function in GAM (x, z = predictors).....	22
Equation 5: Model structure of D ² partitioning for CO ₂ flux based on smooth terms (s) for soil temperature (ST), soil moisture (SM) and interaction tensor (ti).....	22
Equation 6: Calculation of unique D ² for the example of soil moisture (SM).....	22
Equation 7: Calculation of Shannon Entropy.....	23
Equation 8: Calculation of Mutual Information.....	23
Equation 9: Calculation of Relative Mutual Information.....	23